

1 **SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERISATION AND BEHAVIOUR OF**
2 **Co/HYDROXYAPATITE CATALYSTS IN THE OXIDATION OF**
3 **1,2-DICHLOROETHANE**

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24 **Abstract**

25 Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite (HAP) loaded with different amounts of cobalt are
26 synthesised and characterised by several techniques including N₂ physisorption, XRD,
27 TEM, H₂-TPR, UV-Visible-NIR DRS, XPS spectroscopy and volumetric adsorption of
28 CO₂ and NH₃ molecules techniques. The Co(x)/HAP catalysts are tested in the
29 oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane. Due to significant enhancement of the textural and
30 structural properties the resulting Co/hydroxyapatite catalysts achieve higher activity
31 compared to bulk Co₃O₄ catalyst confirming the advantage of dispersing cobalt on a
32 relatively high surface area HAP. Hydroxyapatite support shows a high selectivity
33 towards intermediate reaction products; but its activity suffers a significant decay with
34 time due to chlorination. However, high stability and high selectivity towards deep
35 oxidation products are favoured by Co-rich catalysts.

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47 *Keywords:* Hydroxyapatite, Ion-exchanged Co²⁺, Co₃O₄, Surface chemistry, DCE total
48 oxidation

49 **1. Introduction**

50 Due to the increasing awareness of the negative effects of emissions of volatile organic
51 compounds (VOCs) the industrialised countries governments are imposing rigorous
52 legislations. The essential objective is to minimise these emissions under specific
53 standards in order to maintain the equilibrium in the global energy balance and to
54 reduce direct health risks [1-3]. The presence of chlorine atoms in the chemical structure
55 makes them even more resistant to degradation [2-4]. These chlorinated VOCs (Cl-
56 VOCs) are essentially associated with different industrial activities which release a wide
57 variety of molecular compounds. The Cl-VOCs generally include polychloromethanes,
58 polychloroethanes and polychloroethylenes compounds which possess high volatility
59 and strong resistance to destruction [2-5].

60 Though a number of studies dealing with remediation technologies for removal and
61 decomposition of Cl-VOCs are presently available [6-10], thermal incineration is
62 considered by far the most effective strategies [2,7]. However, it requires high operation
63 temperatures (>700 °C), thereby increasing the processing cost and NO_x emissions. To
64 overcome these drawbacks the catalytic oxidation appears to be a good alternative
65 allowing lower operating temperatures and better control of the reaction products [11-
66 18]. Thus, the synthesis of active and stable catalysts for Cl-VOCs oxidation at low
67 temperature and with high selectivity towards complete oxidation products, i.e. CO_2 ,
68 H_2O and HCl/Cl_2 is receiving increasing attention in the literature [11-18].

69 A considerable number of suitable catalytic systems, including noble metals [19-21] and
70 transition metals [11, 12, 14, 22, 23, 24], have been investigated for total oxidation of
71 chlorinated compounds. As major drawbacks of expensive noble metals are adsorption
72 of chlorine species on the active surface and sintering of the metal active sites at high
73 temperatures [14]. Transition metal oxides (V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Nb, and Mo)

74 appear as a good alternative to noble metal catalysts because of their low cost and their
75 resistance to chlorine poisoning [2, 11, 12, 14, 24].
76 Despite their high activity in the oxidation of hydrocarbons and carbon monoxide cobalt
77 catalysts have scarcely attracted attention concerning their applicability in the removal
78 of chlorinated volatile compounds. The few available investigations dealing with this
79 formulation demonstrated their promising performance for Cl-VOCs removal [11, 12,
80 14]. We previously studied the catalytic performance of a series of bulk Co_3O_4 catalysts
81 prepared by a variety of routes in the gas-phase oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane [11],
82 resulting in considerably higher activity and stability than supported noble metals (Pt,
83 Pd), protonic zeolites, and Ce/Zr and Mn/Zr mixed oxides. This catalytic performance
84 of bulk Co_3O_4 catalysts was related to the oxygen mobility and the acid character of
85 surface active sites. In this sense, Cai et al. [14] studied the influence of modifying the
86 Co_3O_4 structure, by incorporation of small amount of Mn, on the catalytic activity in the
87 oxidation of 1,2-dichlorobenzene. They reported that Mn species retarded the oxygen
88 mobility of surface active oxygen and increased Co^{2+} concentration which had a
89 positive effect on activity, selectivity and stability of $\text{Mn}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ catalyst.
90 Though less detailed and numerous, some papers dedicated to this environmental
91 application have also dealt with the textural properties improvement of Co_3O_4 by means
92 of its dispersion on conventional supports (alumina, zeolite, SiO_2). However, it was
93 proved that this route significantly reduces the activity due to the formation of inactive
94 Co species. For example, Chintawar et al. [25] reported that Co loaded zeolite Y and
95 alumina catalysts were not feasible for the complete catalytic oxidation of chlorinated
96 ethylenes. Generally, in the case of cobalt alumina supported catalysts, an interaction
97 between cobalt oxide and catalyst support could result in incorporation of some
98 Al^{3+} ions into Co_3O_4 spinel matrix resulting in $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{Co}^{3+}_{2-x}\text{Al}_x\text{O}_4$ mixed spinels which

99 would hinder the reduction of Co_3O_4 particles and their oxygen mobility capacity [25,
100 26].

101 Hydroxyapatite, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ (HAP), has been intensively investigated as porous
102 support [27-34]. The interest was justified by the presence of phosphate groups which
103 stabilise the structure of active sites and allow the tuning of acid-base properties by
104 varying the calcium/phosphorus ratio. Moreover, the ability of hydroxyapatite to
105 undergo cation and anion exchanges, due to the presence of two types of zeolite-like
106 channels, leads to modulate its chemical properties without damaging its typical
107 hexagonal structure [28]. These characteristics confer to hydroxyapatite catalysts the
108 generation of new synergic metal-support interactions which could improve their
109 catalytic activity [35-41]. Particularly Moffat's group [35, 40] found promising results
110 on the destruction of chlorinated compounds over this type of catalysts.

111 The aim of this work is the investigation of the textural, structural, surface chemistry
112 and catalytic behaviour of a series of calcium deficient hydroxyapatite-supported cobalt
113 samples in the total oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE), selected as one of the most
114 important chlorinated pollutants emitted in gaseous industrial waste streams [3, 11]. The
115 choice of HAP was made because of the possibility of the control of the Co-support
116 interaction. In this sense, due to its low capacity to exchange Co^{2+} ions (<1.4%) it was
117 expected that this might limit the aforementioned loss of Co active phase compared to
118 conventional supports. The characterisation of the prepared samples involved a wide
119 number of techniques including BET, TEM, XRD, H_2 -TPR, FTIR, UV-visible-NIR
120 DRS, XPS spectroscopy and volumetric adsorption of NH_3 and CO_2 as well-known
121 probe molecules for acid and basic sites, respectively. Cobalt ion-exchanged
122 hydroxyapatite catalyst is also prepared in order to be used as reference. To the best of

123 our knowledge, the applicability of these catalytic materials in the gas-phase oxidation
124 of DCE reaction has not been yet investigated.

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126 **2. Experimental**

127 **2.1. Preparation of the catalysts**

128 Hydroxyapatite support (HAP) was synthesised adding dropwise a boiling aqueous
129 solution of calcium nitrate to a solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$. The precipitate was re-
130 dissolved in a nitric acid solution and neutralised with ammonia at pH 10. The resulting
131 mixture was maintained under stirring at 80 °C for 16 h. After filtration, the recovered
132 solid was thoroughly washed with purified water, then dried at 120 °C and finally
133 calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

134 Cobalt loaded HAP catalysts were prepared by incipient wetness impregnation using
135 solutions containing varying amounts of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The impregnated samples
136 were dried in air at 110 °C for 12 h and subsequently calcined for 4 h, at 500 °C. The
137 resulting samples will be hereafter referred as $\text{Co}(x)/\text{HAP}$. The loaded amount of cobalt
138 was represented by 'x' and it corresponded to the actual Co weight percentage in the
139 catalyst. The final chemical composition was confirmed by means of ICP analysis.

140 An ion-exchanged sample, $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, was also prepared at room temperature by
141 introducing 10 g of HAP into 1000 cm^3 of aqueous solution containing $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
142 (2g). After stirring for 24 h the solid recovered after filtration was washed, dried at 120
143 °C and finally calcined at 500 °C.

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145 **2.2. Characterisation techniques**

146 The volumetric N_2 adsorption at -196 °C was performed on an automatic apparatus
147 Micromeritics, model TRISTAR II 3020 apparatus. The pre-treatments applied to the

148 samples consisted of a cleaning, at 300 °C (overnight), under nitrogen flow. The
149 specific areas of the samples were determined in line with the standard BET procedure,
150 using nitrogen adsorption taken in the relative equilibrium pressure interval of 0.03-0.3.
151 X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were conducted on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray
152 diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The X-ray tube was
153 operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° and 100° (2θ),
154 and the X-ray diffraction line positions were determined with a step size of 0.01° and a
155 counting time of 2.5 s per step. Phase identification was conducted by comparison with
156 JCPDS database cards. From the XRD data, the degree of crystallinity of the
157 synthesised HAP was estimated using the following equation (1) [42]:

$$158 \quad d_c = \left(\frac{K}{B_{(002)}} \right)^3 \quad (1)$$

159 where d_c is the degree of crystallinity, B_{002} is full width at half maximum (°) of
160 reflection (002) and K is a characteristic constant for HAP structures found equal to
161 0.24. Moreover, the Co_3O_4 crystallite size was calculated by Scherrer equation, using
162 Co_3O_4 (311) ($2\theta = 37.1^\circ$) diffraction line broadening.

163 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) absorption spectra were recorded in the
164 400-4000 cm^{-1} range with a Cary 600 Series FTIR spectrometer using disks of samples
165 diluted in KBr. The oxidation states and the coordination of Co were evaluated by
166 diffuse reflectance UV-vis spectroscopy (UV-Visible-NIR DRS) with a UV-vis-NIR
167 Cary 5000 apparatus coupled to Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500 within a range of
168 200–2500 nm.

169 XPS spectra were recorded on a Phoibos 150 1D-DLD analysis system from Specs,
170 with monochromatic Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV). The hemispheric photoelectron
171 analyser worked with a pass energy of 40 eV for survey scan and 20 eV for detail scan.

172 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations were carried out with a Philips
173 CM200 transmission electron microscope equipped with LaB₆ filament operating at
174 200 kV. The sample powder was dispersed in ethanol, dropped on copper grids, coated
175 with lacey carbon film, and evaporated at room temperature.

176 Redox behaviour was examined by temperature-programmed reduction (H₂-TPR) on a
177 Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument. Firstly, all the samples were pre-treated in
178 an oxygen stream (5%O₂/He) at 400 °C for 1 h and then cooled to room temperature.
179 The reducing gas used in all experiments was 5%H₂/Ar, with a flow rate of 50 cm³ min⁻¹
180 ¹. The temperature range explored was from room temperature to 1000 °C, with a
181 heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. This temperature was maintained for 30 min. The water
182 produced by reduction was trapped in a cold trap, and the consumption of H₂ was
183 quantitatively measured by time integration of the TPR profiles.

184 The acid/base properties of the catalysts were determined by NH₃-pulse/CO₂-pulse
185 experiments carried out at 120 °C. The samples were submitted to a pre-treatment
186 routine consisting of heating in a flow of 5%O₂/He, at 500 °C (30 min), and cooling
187 down to 120 °C in a flow of He. NH₃ or CO₂ pulses were then injected in a He carrier
188 over the sample during 30 s, with a time interval between pulses of 10 min. The NH₃ or
189 CO₂ signal was online analysed online with an automatic apparatus Micromeritics,
190 AutoChem 2920 instrument, equipped with thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

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192 **2.3. Catalytic tests**

193 Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed bed reactor operated at
194 atmospheric pressure. The reactor was made of quartz with an internal diameter of
195 10 mm and a height of 300 mm, in which the temperature is controlled with a
196 thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.85 g of catalyst in powdered form

197 (0.3–0.5 mm) was loaded. The reaction feed consisted of 1000 ppm of DCE in dry air
198 with a total gas flow of $500 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ($15,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$). It should be noted that the
199 experimental conditions employed in this work were chosen to meet the criteria to
200 ensure the absence of the mass and heat transfer limitations, as described elsewhere
201 [11]. Catalytic activity was measured over the range 150-500 °C and conversion data
202 were calculated by the difference between inlet and outlet concentrations. Conversion
203 measurements and product profiles were taken at steady state, typically after 30 minutes
204 on stream.

205 The feed and effluent streams were analysed using an on-line 7980A Agilent
206 Technologies gas chromatograph equipped with a thermal conductivity (CO and CO₂)
207 and an electron capture detector (chlorinated hydrocarbons). Analysis of HCl and
208 Cl₂ was carried out by means of ion selective electrode and titration, respectively.
209 Further details on analytical procedures can be found elsewhere [11]. On basis of the
210 concentrations [Ci] at the outlet of the reactor, product yields (CO₂, CO, vinyl chloride
211 (VC: C₂H₃Cl), HCl and Cl₂) were calculated, according to the following equations:

$$212 \quad S_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{[\text{CO}_2]}{2[\text{VC}] + [\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (2)$$

$$213 \quad S_{\text{CO}} = \frac{[\text{CO}]}{2[\text{VC}] + [\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (3)$$

$$214 \quad S_{\text{VC}} = \frac{2[\text{VC}]}{2[\text{VC}] + [\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (4)$$

$$215 \quad S_{\text{HCl}} = \frac{[\text{HCl}]}{2[\text{Cl}_2] + [\text{CV}] + [\text{HCl}]} \quad (5)$$

$$216 \quad S_{\text{Cl}_2} = \frac{2[\text{Cl}_2]}{2[\text{Cl}_2] + [\text{CV}] + [\text{HCl}]} \quad (6)$$

217 **3. Results and discussion**

218 **3.1. Characterisation of the samples**

219 **3.1.1. Chemical analysis**

220 Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the HAP-supported cobalt catalyst along
221 with that of the bare support. Judging from the obtained results, the synthesised support
222 consists of a calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite with Ca/P molar ratio equal to 1.50,
223 lower than the 1.67 expected for a stoichiometric hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$).
224 According to many authors this non-stoichiometry can be explained by loss of Ca^{2+}
225 ions, which is corrected by insertion of H^+ ions at the expense of hydroxyl groups to
226 ensure electroneutrality [43-44]. Hence, the general formula of these calcium deficient
227 hydroxyapatite can be denoted as $\text{Ca}_{10-z}(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$ where $0 < z \leq 1$. The
228 Ca/P ratio corresponding to Co(IE)-HAP sample, prepared by ion-exchange method, is
229 relatively lower (1.20), thereby suggesting that the substituted Ca^{2+} ions were lixiviated
230 during the filtration process. By contrast, for the five impregnated Co(x)/HAP samples,
231 the Ca/P ratio is quite similar (about 1.5) which evidenced no further loss of calcium.
232 On the other hand, the cobalt loadings are found to be ranged between 1.1-19.6wt.%
233 (Table 1). This wide range could allow us to study the evolution of the samples
234 properties, with the progressive increase of Co surface density, from sub-monolayer to
235 over-monolayer densities. Note that the theoretical monolayer estimation
236 (corresponding to a cobalt loading of 8.1wt.%) is made in accordance with that
237 proposed for the monolayer of cobalt supported on alumina as to reach a surface density
238 of 16 Co atoms nm^{-2} [45].

239

240 **3.1.2. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

241 The experimental N₂ physisorption isotherms for Co(x)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts
242 (not shown) and the data reported in Table 1 show that the isotherms were characteristic
243 of mesoporous materials exhibiting IV-type according to the IUPAC classification. Fig.

244 1 shows the pore size distributions for all the prepared catalysts. The pore size
245 distribution corresponding to HAP support and the Co(x)/HAP catalysts ($x \leq 11.2\text{wt.}\%$)
246 show a broad unimodal distribution centred at approximately 30 nm (Fig. 1). However,
247 at high Co loading (19.6wt.%) a slight shift of the distribution peak towards lower
248 values (25 nm) is observed. On the other hand, the increased addition of cobalt to HAP
249 produces a progressive drop in its specific surface area (up to 25%) and pore volume
250 (up to 39%). For instance, the specific surface area of the resultant catalysts
251 significantly decreases from $55 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for the HAP bare support to $41 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for
252 Co(11.2)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts.

253

254 **3.1.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

255 The Co(x)/HAP catalysts were characterised by means of X-ray powder diffraction in
256 order to investigate their structural properties. The diffractogram of the HAP support
257 calcined at 500 °C, Fig. 2A, is identical to the hexagonal hydroxyapatite structure
258 presenting a $P6_3/m$ space group (JCPDS: 74-0565). Moreover, the degree of
259 crystallinity of the prepared HAP is estimated to be around 0.8. This is in agreement
260 with an earlier study reporting that the calcination of apatite materials at or above 500
261 °C could lead to a crystallinity degree of about 0.7-0.8 [46]. It should be pointed out that
262 the presence of hydroxyapatite as unique phase, on the HAP diffractogram, confirms
263 that its structure is tolerant to deviation from the stoichiometry. Yet, the formation of β -
264 tricalcium phosphate as a product of hydroxyapatite decomposition is not expected after
265 calcination at 500 °C [44].

266 The diffractograms of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts show no lines
267 corresponding to cobalt oxides crystals (Fig. 2A) probably because of their high
268 dispersion and/or the fact that the formed crystallites are smaller than their detection

269 limit. With these limitations spectroscopic measurements could present an alternative
270 option to characterise these samples because well-resolved spectra could be obtained
271 with small Co loadings. At higher Co concentration, 4.3-19.6%, two additional typical
272 peaks belonging to Co_3O_4 spinel structure, JCPDS 76-1802, appeared at $2\theta = 31.6^\circ$ and
273 37.1° (Fig. 2A). Their intensity increases, as expected, with cobalt loading. Table 1 also
274 reports the Co_3O_4 crystal size calculated by Scherrer equation. The average size of the
275 Co_3O_4 particles is around 24-32 nm on the $\text{Co}(x)/\text{HAP}$ catalysts ($x \geq 4.3\%$).

276

277 **3.1.4. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

278 The catalysts with low Co loadings, $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, were investigated
279 by TEM in order to estimate the Co species particle sizes, not detected by XRD. The
280 micrographs of the two samples show some differences in morphology. On the $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-}$
281 HAP catalyst some scratched dark areas and zones presenting low contrast are observed.
282 The presence of the former may be related with well crystallised HAP areas where some
283 of its reticular planes form channels in which the Co ions are incorporated. The
284 measured distance between visible diffraction plans is approximately 0.8 nm.
285 Examination of $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ micrograph reveals the presence of similar areas observed
286 on the $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$ catalyst together with small Co particles, ranged between 6-10 nm,
287 which have a quasi spherical shape. Since the two samples are loaded with the same
288 amount of Co, 1.1wt.%, these observations are probably related with the method used
289 for the preparation of each catalyst and the subsequent distribution of formed Co
290 species. As will be shown later, the apparition of Co species with relatively high particle
291 sizes on the impregnated sample ($\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$) compared to $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, prepared by
292 ion exchange method, may be explained by the growth of some Co species on the
293 support surface.

294 **3.1.5. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

295 FTIR spectroscopy is commonly used to complete the structural characterisation of
296 apatite materials made by means of XRD techniques. The objective is essentially to
297 confirm the presence of hydroxyls and phosphate groups and the presence or the
298 absence of some derived phosphate groups like $(\text{HPO}_4)^{2-}$ anions. Fig. 4 includes the
299 FTIR spectra for HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts. The recorded spectrum corresponding
300 to HAP bare support is characteristic of non-stoichiometric hydroxyapatite structures
301 (Fig. 4). The five bands centred at 566, 602, 960, 1035 and 1095 cm^{-1} are assigned to
302 different vibration modes of P-O bonds in the $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ groups [27-28, 47]. Moreover, the
303 vibration of hydroxyls groups hosted by the apatite framework is evidenced by the
304 presence of a small sharp band at 3575 cm^{-1} and a more intense feature at 630 cm^{-1} . It
305 should be noted that, as expected, in agreement with the ICP results, the spectrum of
306 HAP sample presents a band around 875 cm^{-1} which attests the presence of $(\text{HPO}_4)^{2-}$
307 ions; typical of calcium deficient hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10-z}(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$). The
308 HAP spectrum also shows additional bands attributed to adsorbed water (1630 and 3400
309 cm^{-1}) and carbonates (1385 cm^{-1}) [27-28, 48].

310 It should be noted that no significant changes are detected on the Co(IE)-HAP spectrum
311 compared with the bare support. However, the samples prepared by impregnation
312 displayed a new band at 663 cm^{-1} which increases with the Co loading (Fig. 4). The
313 signal is attributed to the Co-O stretching vibration characteristic of spinel Co_3O_4 [48-
314 51]. Moreover, new shoulders appear at higher Co loading which affected the
315 absorption of the water molecule vibrations in the 3200-3600 cm^{-1} range. Jones et al.
316 [52] reported that this effect could indicate the presence of water coordinated to the
317 metal ion. By contrast, at low loading the Co ion-exchanged is the dominant Co species
318 which does not significantly disturb the vibrations of adsorbed water molecules.

319 3.1.6. UV-Visible-NIR diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-Visible-NIR DRS)

320 Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was used to study the symmetry and the oxidation
321 state of cobalt species dispersed on the HAP support. It is known that, in normal Co_3O_4
322 spinel structure, the Co^{2+} ions ($3d^7$) occupy tetrahedral coordination (Td) while the Co^{3+}
323 ions ($3d^6$) host an octahedral surrounding (Oh). The optical spectra of these Co species
324 are generally composed of i) three spin allowed d-d transitions in the visible region
325 corresponding to Co^{3+} Oh symmetry and ii) three transitions in the visible and NIR
326 regions for the Co^{2+} Td coordination. Moreover, the interaction between the two Co
327 sites can produce additional absorption bands due to metal to metal charge transfer
328 distributed between the visible and NIR regions.

329 Fig. 5 displays the UV-visible-NIR spectra for the prepared $\text{Co}(x)/\text{HAP}$ samples. A
330 spectrum of bulk Co_3O_4 , prepared by decomposition of cobalt nitrate at 500°C , is also
331 analysed for comparison. The HAP spectrum exhibits absorption bands in the NIR
332 region related to surface hydroxyls groups, 1300-1500 nm, and another one assigned to
333 structural OH groups, 1900-2100 nm (Fig. 5) [27,28]. In the UV region, a band around
334 200 nm, ascribed to $\text{O}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Ca}^{2+}$ charge transfers [27,28], is also observed.

335 The spectrum of the ion-exchanged sample, $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, is characterised by the
336 presence of three d-d transitions bands between 520-630 nm, in the visible region, and a
337 broad band extended in the NIR domain (1000-1800 nm) (Fig. 5). Similar spectra were
338 obtained in previous works dealing with the characterisation of cobalt at cation
339 exchange sites. For instance, in their study on spectroscopy and coordination chemistry
340 of cobalt in molecular sieves Verberckmoes et al. [53] reported that these absorptions
341 could be assigned to ν_3 (${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$) and ν_1 (${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$) transitions of the
342 octahedral Co^{2+} located in cation exchange sites. From these results we can conclude

343 that, in Co(IE)-HAP sample, the exchanged Co^{2+} species are probably hosted by
344 octahedral sites.

345 On the other hand, the impregnated samples spectra show a striking similarity with the
346 bulk Co_3O_4 spectrum (Fig. 5). The absorption bands centred at 1200-1500 nm and 670
347 nm are attributed to ν_1 (${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F})$) and ν_2 (${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$) transitions, respectively,
348 which correspond to tetrahedral Co^{2+} [54]. Likewise, the presence of octahedral Co^{3+}
349 ions is evidenced by their characteristic d-d transitions bands, centred at 750 nm and
350 350-460 nm, associated with ν_1 (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{1g}$) and ν_2 (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{2g}$), respectively [54]. It
351 is relevant to highlight that the latter shifts towards the UV domain with Co loading
352 (from 460 nm for Co(1.1)/HAP to 350 nm for the catalysts with higher Co loading).
353 This suggests the growth of tridimensional and well crystallised Co_3O_4 on these Co-rich
354 samples. By contrast, despite the presence of Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} ions on the Co(1.1)/HAP
355 sample its spectrum shows a difference respect to those corresponding to
356 Co($4.5 \leq x \leq 19.6$)/HAP. Moreover, it was observed that the color turned from grey for the
357 Co(1.1)/HAP to black for the Co($4.5 \leq x \leq 19.6$)/HAP catalysts. According to earlier
358 studies [55], these observations clearly indicate that on the Co(1.1)/HAP catalyst the Co
359 could form Co_xO_y clusters composed of a mixture of octahedral Co^{3+} and tetrahedral
360 Co^{2+} . These can be considered as precursors of Co_3O_4 nanocrystals. These results are in
361 agreement with the findings from TEM and XRD analyses. The Co species particles
362 (<10 nm) found on the Co(1.1)/HAP are much smaller than those corresponding to
363 Co($4.5 \leq x \leq 19.6$)/HAP catalysts, in the 23-32 nm range. It is worth mentioning that the
364 presence of exchanged Co^{2+} species in the impregnated Co(x)/HAP samples can not be
365 ruled out since their absorption bands may overlap with those of spinel Co_3O_4 structure.

366

367 **3.1.7. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)**

368 The influence of the Co content on the surface distribution of cobalt species has been
369 investigated by means of XPS techniques. Fig. 6 and Table 2 summarise the
370 corresponding results. The Co 2p XPS spectra for all the Co(x)/HAP samples have been
371 processed while maintaining the Co 2p_{3/2}/Co 2p_{1/2} area ratio at approximately 2 (Fig. 6).
372 The Co 2p_{3/2} spectra consist of a main photoemission peak (M) located at a binding
373 energy (BE) in the range of 780.8-783 eV and a satellite peak (S) attributed to a shake-
374 up process, appearing at approximately 6-8 eV higher BE.

375 In the Co 2p_{3/2} region, the XPS profile for the Co(IE)-HAP catalyst exhibits two peaks,
376 centred at 783.1 and 788.9 eV, attributed to Co²⁺ and its typical shake-up satellite peak,
377 respectively. As expected, the impregnation of cobalt onto the HAP surface slightly
378 shifts the Co 2p_{3/2} main peak position to lower BE, compared to Co(IE)-HAP sample,
379 suggesting the near surface enrichment with Co³⁺ ions (Fig. 6 and Table 2) [54]. The
380 main Co 2p_{3/2} peak corresponding to Co(8.5)/HAP, Co(11.2)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP
381 tend to split into two signals corresponding to two distinct contributions. The first one
382 centred at 780.8 eV is attributed to Co³⁺ ions while the shoulder situated at 783.2±0.2 eV
383 is assigned to Co²⁺ species. These results are in good agreement with the FTIR and DRS
384 studies and clearly corroborated the previous findings by evidencing the formation of
385 Co₃O₄ crystals in the impregnated Co(x≥4.3)/HAP samples. This conclusion is also
386 supported by the spin-orbit splitting (ΔE) and S/M ratio values reported in Table 2.

387 Indeed, the observed decrease in these two parameters with increasing Co content
388 suggests the evolution towards a major contribution of Co³⁺ ions and, then, the
389 deposition of spinel Co₃O₄ structure [54]. For instance, the measured ΔE decreases from
390 16.4 eV for Co(IE)-HAP catalyst to 15 eV for Co(8.5)/HAP Co(11.2)/HAP and
391 Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts. Likewise, the calculated S/M values decrease from 0.60 for
392 Co(IE)-HAP to 0.39 for Co(11.2)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts.

393 Table 2 also offers a comparison between the Co/Ca molar ratios calculated from the
394 XPS and ICP data. When comparing the Co/Ca molar ratio values of Co(IE)-HAP and
395 Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts, having the same Co content (1.1wt.%) but prepared by different
396 methods, it is observed that it is higher in the ion-exchanged sample. This higher Co/Ca
397 ratio value can be explained by the substitution of Ca^{2+} ions lixiviated during the
398 filtration process, by Co^{2+} ions.

399

400 **3.1.8. Temperature programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR)**

401 The H_2 -TPR experiments were performed in order to investigate the reducibility of
402 different Co species present in the Co(x)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts. To our
403 knowledge, similar H_2 -TPR study, concerning the Co/HAP materials, has not been yet
404 published. Fig. 7 displays the H_2 -TPR profiles of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP for
405 different Co loadings. Table 3 reports the quantitative data calculated from the
406 integration of the resulted reduction peaks. Fig. 7 shows that no reduction peak was
407 found on the HAP bare support. The diagram of Co(IE)-HAP sample shows a broad
408 reduction peak at high temperature (>500 °C), associated with the reduction of
409 exchanged Co^{2+} ions. As shown in Table 3, the integration of this reduction peak gives a
410 value of H_2 consumption of 0.29 mmol g^{-1} (1.14% Co^{2+}). This is consistent with our
411 above mentioned proposal (the presence of exchanged Co^{2+} as unique Co phase) since it
412 was close to the overall Co content (1.1%) determined by ICP.

413 Fig.7 also shows the H_2 -TPR traces corresponding to Co(x)/HAP impregnated catalysts.
414 In this series of catalysts, the reduction profiles are quite similar. Hence, they are
415 characterised by the presence of two typical reduction peaks of bulk Co_3O_4 , in the 250-
416 500 °C temperature range, and a reduction peak due to the exchanged Co^{2+} ions at high
417 temperatures (>500 °C). The Co_3O_4 reduction process takes place realised through two

418 steps consisting of the reduction of Co^{3+} ions to Co^{2+} (peak around 300-330 °C)
419 accompanied by much more intense reduction peak due to the reduction of Co^{2+} ions to
420 metallic cobalt (375-430 °C) [11]. As revealed by the sixth column data reported in
421 Table 3, the H_2/Co molar ratio values (1.4-1.5) corresponding to the low reduction
422 peaks temperatures (<500 °C) for $\text{Co}(8.5 \leq x \leq 19.6)/\text{HAP}$ catalysts are close to 1.33,
423 expected for stoichiometric Co_3O_4 . By contrast, for the $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ sample this value
424 is significantly higher (3.4) suggesting the deposition of non-stoichiometric Co_3O_4 . The
425 latter is in good agreement with our characterisation results, discussed above, which
426 suggested the formation of Co_xO_y clusters composed of a mixture of octahedral Co^{3+}
427 and tetrahedral Co^{2+} . Fig. 8 reports the relationship between the overall Co content
428 determined by ICP and the contribution of the two phases of Co, ion-exchanged and
429 deposited as Co_3O_4 or Co_xO_y , calculated from the integration of the corresponding
430 reduction peaks. The amount of Co ion-exchanged species increases slowly with the Co
431 loading from 0.67% on $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ up to 1.34%, on the $\text{Co}(11.2)/\text{HAP}$ catalyst, above
432 which remains unchanged with Co loading. However, the contribution of Co spread as
433 Co_3O_4 or Co_xO_y over the carrier linearly increases with Co loading.

434

435 **3.1.9. Volumetric adsorption studies**

436 The acid-base properties of the prepared catalysts were investigated by means of
437 volumetric adsorption techniques. NH_3 and CO_2 were used as probe molecules to
438 determine the acid and basic surface densities, respectively. Twenty consecutive pulses
439 at 120 °C separated by 10 min evacuation treatment at the same temperature were
440 recorded. In general, the first pulses of reactive gas are sufficient to reach the maximum
441 adsorption capacity of the samples. Then, the adsorption data are determined from the

442 difference between the first and second experimental pulses. The corresponding data are
443 included in Table 3.

444 Hence, the surface density for NH₃ adsorption sites on HAP support is 1.45 μmol m⁻²
445 whereas it does not adsorb more than 0.22 μmol m⁻² of CO₂. This difference is
446 explained by the calcium deficiency of the support which leads to a surface with a
447 notable acidic character [27-28]. This is why in the case of the Co(IE)-HAP sample,
448 presenting a substitution of Ca²⁺ by Co²⁺ ions, the density of surface acidity is, even
449 more, enhanced (1.93 μmol m⁻²) at the expense of the surface basicity (0.11 μmol m⁻²).

450 Though not proceeding via analogous pathway the impregnation of cobalt onto the HAP
451 surface influences dramatically the amount of the adsorbed NH₃ and CO₂. According
452 to Table 3, the surface density of adsorbed CO₂ on the support, 0.22 μmol m⁻², is much
453 smaller than that determined for Co(x)/HAP, 0.45-0.54 μmol m⁻². Likewise, the surface
454 acidity slightly increases with the addition of small amounts of Co (≤ 4.3%), but it
455 notably decreases for the samples with high Co loadings (≥ 8.5%). For example the
456 surface density of adsorbed NH₃ results in 2.26 μmol m⁻² for Co(1.1)/HAP while around
457 1.11 μmol m⁻² in the case of the Co(8.5)/HAP catalyst. This drastic change in the acid
458 character on the Co(x)/HAP catalysts can be explained by the achievement of Co
459 monolayer densities which cover totally the support surface and, then, minimise their
460 surface acidity. However, for all the Co(x)/HAP catalysts, the surface basicity becomes
461 twice compared to bare HAP support.

462

463 **3.2. Catalytic behaviour in the oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE)**

464 The DCE oxidation reaction was examined over the calcined catalysts in the
465 temperature window between 150 and 500 °C, by sequentially increasing the reaction
466 temperature with 25 °C intervals (light-off curves). Fig. 9A displays the evolution of

467 DCE conversion (X_{DCE}) over the Co(x)/HAP catalysts versus reaction temperature.
468 With the reactor filled up with pure HAP the reaction begins around 200 °C and
469 increased slowly up to 300 °C. Then it started to increase rapidly with reaction
470 temperature. At 450 °C, the DCE conversion is close to 100%. Over the Co(IE)-HAP
471 ion-exchanged catalyst the reaction ignition starts at 275 °C and the conversion
472 increases slowly with the temperature, but it does not exceed 83% at 500 °C. The shape
473 of activity traces for Co(x)/HAP impregnated catalysts is almost similar compared to
474 that of HAP support. Table 4 compares the obtained results in terms of temperatures at
475 which the DCE conversion reached 10 (T_{10}), 50 (T_{50}), and 90% (T_{90}). Some recently
476 published results for a bulk Co_3O_4 oxide ($11 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) are used as reference for
477 comparison [59]. Data in Table 4 show that the catalytic activity, on the basis of T_{50}
478 values, follows this trend: Co(4.3)/HAP (325 °C) > HAP (335 °C) > Co(1.1)/HAP (345
479 °C) > Co(11.2)/HAP > Co(8.5)/HAP ~ Co(19.6)/HAP > Co(IE)-HAP (360 °C) > Co_3O_4
480 (380 °C). This tendency proves the comparable potential of HAP support in comparison
481 with the cobalt catalysts to decompose DCE. Table 4 also shows activity data referred to
482 1 g of catalyst and 1 m^2 of BET surface area. On the HAP sample the specific catalytic
483 activity is around $2.4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ suggesting that Ca-deficient hydroxyapatite
484 is not an inert support when applied in DCE oxidation reaction. For the series of
485 Co(x)/HAP impregnated catalysts the specific catalytic activity value seems to increase
486 with the cobalt loading from 3.9×10^{-10} for Co(1.1)/HAP to $7.1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2}$
487 s^{-1} for Co(11.2)/HAP catalyst but it remains almost constant for the catalyst with the
488 highest copper loading (19.6%). It is worth outlining that the Co(IE)-HAP catalyst
489 shows the lowest activity ($0.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) with respect to the Co(x)/HAP
490 catalysts. Besides, when compared to the low specific activity of pure Co_3O_4 (0.24
491 $\times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) the notable improved textural and structural properties of the

492 resulting Co/hydroxyapatite catalysts make them advantageously more active than the
493 bulk spinel.

494 Table 4 summarises the values of the apparent activation energy (E_a) for the Co(x)/HAP
495 catalysts. The corresponding calculations are made assuming a first order reaction and a
496 linear correlation is obtained between $\ln[-\ln(1-X_{DCE})]$ and $1/T$ (Fig. 10). The analysis of
497 the obtained results shows that relatively high activation energy values, 105-108 kJ mol^{-1}
498 ¹, are obtained on the HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts. However, the E_a values decrease
499 significantly with the supported cobalt phases to reach values about 58-62 kJ mol^{-1} over
500 Co($x \geq 8.3\%$), close to those exhibited by the bulk Co_3O_4 prepared by different routes
501 (53-56 kJ mol^{-1}) [59].

502

503 **3.3. Structure-activity-selectivity relationships**

504 In their study on the methanol oxidation reaction over Co/hydroxyapatite Aellach et al.
505 [37] concluded that the redox properties of Co_3O_4 and acid properties of the apatite
506 support led to a very efficient catalyst compared to bulk Co_3O_4 . Moreover, the presence
507 of surface cationic vacancies on the Ca-deficient hydroxyapatite can improve the
508 catalytic activity. This might explain the low activity of our Co(IE)-HAP catalyst. The
509 characterization of the latter has confirmed the presence of hardly reducible Co^{2+} (ion-
510 exchanged) as unique Co phase. Then, the poor performance can be related to an
511 inactivity of this Co species and the absence of surface cationic vacancies which are
512 occupied by the Co^{2+} ions. The relatively higher activity of HAP, compared to that of
513 Co(IE)-HAP, can support our claim; especially, the former contains cation vacancies
514 due to its Ca-deficiency.

515 On the other hand, the increase of the activity over the Co(x)/HAP samples with the
516 increase of Co loadings can be explained by the surface Co_3O_4 enrichment which

517 contains easily reducible Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} species. This is in good agreement with the
518 relatively comparable activation energy determined on the Co-rich samples and bulk
519 Co_3O_4 (Table 4). This suggests that the activity is controlled by similar near surface
520 composition, characterised by an abundance of Co_3O_4 crystals. On pure Co_3O_4 the
521 surface density of Co sites is certainly larger than that for Co(x)/HAP supported
522 samples; however, this difference is overcompensated by their much higher surface area
523 and their relatively low Co_3O_4 crystal size (20-25 nm) compared with bulk Co_3O_4 (38
524 nm).

525 Figs. 9 (B, C, D, E and F) show the concentration-temperature profiles of the main
526 oxidation products (CO_2 , CO, VC, HCl and Cl_2 , respectively). Table 4 also includes the
527 carbon balance, CO/ CO_2 and Cl_2 /HCl ratios calculated at 500 °C for each tested
528 catalyst. The formation of CO_2 , as deep DCE oxidation (7) product, seems to be
529 affected by the Co loading and, then, the Co species lying on the surface (Fig. 9B).

531 For the catalysts with Co contents lower than 4.3% the CO_2 production does not exceed
532 100 ppm whereas it notably increased over the high Co loading catalysts ($x \geq 4.3\%$). For
533 instance, on the Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst the CO_2 concentration reaches a maximum of
534 2000 ppm at 500 °C and over Co(4.3)/HAP 1700 ppm of CO_2 is produced at 500 °C. It
535 could be concluded that, in agreement with our characterisation results, formation of
536 CO_2 as a product of the DCE total oxidation should mainly involve the Co_3O_4 species
537 (Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} ions) deposited on the support surface which are easily reducible as
538 reported in H_2 -TPR section. Conversely, the yield of CO is markedly favoured (Fig. 9C)
539 on the low Co loading catalysts (HAP, Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP). For instance,
540 800 ppm are produced over HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts at 500 °C. Indeed, on the
541 Co(1.1)/HAP catalyst CO/ CO_2 ratio is around 6 while it decreases to about 0.01 on the

542 Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst (Table 4). In their study on the CO oxidation reaction on
543 hydroxyapatite Matsumura et al. [35] reported that the introduction of
544 tetrachloromethane into the feedstream in the CO oxidation process converts, at least
545 partially, the hydroxyapatite to chlorinated apatite that suppresses the oxidation of CO
546 to CO₂. We can conclude that the same phenomenon occurs in the case of our prepared
547 HAP and the very low Co loadings catalysts (1.1%), leading to a large uncovered
548 support surface, which inhibited the CO oxidation to form CO₂. By contrast, based on
549 our characterisation results, it seems that deposited Co₃O₄ spinel phase on the catalysts
550 surface, for Co loadings $\geq 4.3\%$, enhances notably the CO conversion to CO₂.

551 The HAP support effect on the distribution of the DCE oxidation products was also
552 studied by analysing the VC intermediate production curves (Fig. 9D). In the case of
553 HAP, Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts a production peak centred at 425 °C is
554 observed before decreasing sharply for $T \geq 425$ °C with high CO production, as above
555 commented. VC concentration maxima result in 800 ppm with HAP, 400 ppm with
556 Co(1.1)/HAP and 310 ppm with Co(IE)-HAP catalyst. Nevertheless, with Co(4.3)/HAP
557 catalyst, the VC production peak was shifts to lower temperatures (375 °C with a
558 maximum about 300 ppm) compared to the low Co loading catalysts ($x \leq 1.1\%$).

559 Likewise, the amount of the produced VC continues to decline with Co loading when it
560 did not exceed 55 ppm on the Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst. This suggests that the catalysts
561 with low Co loadings and more acid sites are more selective to produce VC compound.

562 Our NH₃ adsorption study, described above, pointed out that catalysts with $Co \leq 4.3\%$
563 have higher surface acid density compared to $Co(8.5 \leq x \leq 19.6)$ /HAP catalysts. This is in
564 good agreement with a number of earlier studies in the literature [57-58] which reveal
565 that acid sites may play a key role for the production of VC at mild temperatures as an

566 intermediate molecule derived from hydrodechlorination of DCE, which should readily
567 decompose finally to CO_x.

568 Fig. 9E and Fig. 9F show the production profiles of HCl and Cl₂, respectively.
569 Generally, HCl is the preferred chlorinated product because it can be easily trapped by
570 aqueous scrubbing [58]. As can be seen in Fig. 9E hydrogen chloride is the main deep
571 DCE oxidation product over the HAP, Co(1.1)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts. For
572 instance, over Co(1.1)/HAP catalyst 1800 ppm of HCl are produced at 475 °C compared
573 to 500 ppm produced over Co(8.5)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts. However,
574 significant amount of molecular chlorine, Cl₂, is formed on the high Co loadings
575 catalysts, $x \geq 4.5\%$, due to the occurrence of the Deacon reaction (reaction 8). At 475 °C,
576 the Cl₂ concentration is about 550 ppm on Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst and 420 ppm on the
577 Co(8.5)/HAP catalyst. Furthermore, as shown in Table 4, at 500 °C the Cl₂/HCl values
578 are relatively higher on the Co(4.5 ≤ x ≤ 19.6)/HAP catalysts (0.6-0.9). By contrast, in the
579 case of the HAP, Co(1.1)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts very small amounts of Cl₂ are
580 detected in all the reaction temperatures analysed range, up to 500 °C (Cl₂/HCl=0.002-
581 0.005).

583

584 **3.4. Characterisation of used catalysts**

585 Textural, structural and surface chemistry analyses were carried out, on the spent
586 samples, in order to study the eventual changes after reaction. The surface analysis of
587 the used catalysts was conducted by XPS techniques, particularly focused on the
588 determination of chlorine and carbon species deposited on the catalysts surface.
589 According to the reported data in Table 2 the amount of accumulated chlorine on the
590 HAP sample results in around 6.8wt.%. This content tends to increase with Co loading

591 up to 10wt.% on the Co(8.5)/HAP catalyst. However, the XPS analysis shows a lower
592 carbon deposition tendency. Indeed, carbon traces are detected on the low Co loading
593 samples only: Co(1.1)/HAP (1.8%) and Co(IE)-HAP (3%). These results are in
594 accordance with the lower carbon balance values found on these two tested catalysts
595 (72% for Co(IE)-HAP and 78% for Co(1.1)/HAP), as stated in Table 4.

596 Irrespective of the spent catalyst, its characterisation by XRD, Fig. 2B, evidences total
597 conversion of the hydroxyapatite into its chlorinated analogue (Cl-AP: $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{Cl}_2$).
598 The diffractogram of this chlorinated framework is particularly characterised by two
599 intense signals at $2\theta = 31.5^\circ$ and 32.4° (JCPDS: 027-0074). The former seems to
600 overlap the peak, centred at 31.6° , attributed to Co_3O_4 structure. Nevertheless, the
601 presence of the diffraction peak at $2\theta = 37.1^\circ$ proves that the spinel is still present on the
602 spent catalysts. Similar observations concerning the phase transformation of
603 hydroxyapatite were found in the literature [35,36]. For instance, Reichle [36] found
604 that gaseous chlorobenzene could react with hydroxyapatite to yield chlorinated apatite.
605 It should be noted that, although the chlorine amounts retained on the surface exceed
606 those required to form stoichiometric Cl-AP, no additional chlorinated phases, such as
607 cobalt(II) chloride or cobalt(II) chlorate, are detected on the spent catalysts by XRD.
608 Nevertheless, it is known that surface cobalt oxides sites adsorb chlorine which results
609 from the destruction of chlorinated compounds [59]. Fig. 11 depicts the effect of the
610 non exchanged cobalt species on the resulting chlorine amount (surface Cl, %),
611 calculated as the difference between the total chlorine amount and that required to form
612 Cl-AP. The analysis of this figure demonstrates that the chlorine amounts increase with
613 the surface Co species up to 4.1%, corresponding to 8.9% of non exchanged cobalt
614 amount (close to 8.1% for theoretical Co monolayer), after which it stay almost
615 constant. This suggests that chlorine species are adsorbed on the surface Co species.

616 On the other hand, the spinel Co_3O_4 ($2\theta = 37.1^\circ$) diffraction line broadening was used to
617 estimate, by Scherrer equation, the evolution of crystallite size after catalytic test (Table
618 1). In this sense, no significant growth of the spinel crystallites is noticed (size
619 estimated to be around 23-28 nm in the fresh sample while it is around 23-32 nm after
620 catalytic test). The BET surface area of all the analysed catalysts notably decreases after
621 reaction (Table 1). For instance, it decreases from 55 to $44 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in the HAP sample
622 and from 41 to $29 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in the Co(19.6)/HAP sample. This loss of specific surface area,
623 in all the spent catalysts, is probably due to the phase transformation of HAP support
624 which is converted to Cl-AP [56].

625

626 **3.5. Catalytic stability**

627 The catalytic stability with time on stream of the HAP support and Co(19.6)/HAP
628 catalysts, in the DCE oxidation process, was investigated by analysing the evolution of
629 DCE conversion and the products selectivity with time on stream at 375°C for 50 h
630 (Fig. 12). In spite of a comparable activity of the two catalysts is observed at the
631 beginning of the experiments (80-85%) the HAP suffers a significant decay with time.
632 For instance, after 50 h HAP shows a conversion lower than 55% whereas it is still
633 around 77% over Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst. In fact, this catalyst shows a stable
634 performance in terms of conversion and selectivity after a reaction time interval of 7 h.
635 The observed good stability of this sample is related to the lower impact of induced
636 chlorination. On the basis of the observed decrease in HCl selectivity during the first
637 seven hours, it is reasonable to think that chlorinated apatite is formed at this time
638 interval. Afterwards stable selectivities to HCl (42%) and Cl_2 (58%) are observed.
639 Interestingly chlorination does not involve significant changes in CO_2 selectivity as it
640 remains constant (above 98%) during the whole time span of the run.

641 By contrast, it seems that the HAP catalytic activity is much more affected by its
642 structural transformation to chlorinated apatite. Moreover, the shape of the HAP activity
643 curves versus time on stream reflects an oscillatory behaviour suggesting the
644 intermittent regeneration of the hydroxyapatite by the produced water (equation 9).
645 Reichle [36] also observed the regeneration phenomenon of the hydroxyapatite structure
646 by steam in the hydrolysis of chlorobenzene. As for product distribution high VC and
647 HCl selectivity, 76% and 70% respectively, are achieved together with significant low
648 CO/CO₂ selectivity values (lower than 20%).

649

650 **4. Conclusions**

651 Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite, with Ca/P ratio of 1.5, was synthesised by
652 precipitation method. The resulted support was impregnated with cobalt and
653 characterised by TEM, BET, XRD, FTIR, H₂-TPR, UV-Visible-NIR DRS, XPS and
654 volumetric adsorption of CO₂ and NH₃ molecules techniques. Three types of cobalt
655 species have been identified in the impregnated Co(x)/HAP catalysts: (i) Co²⁺ ions
656 exchanged with Ca²⁺ ions of the apatite framework, (ii) Co_xO_y clusters with small
657 particle size (<10 nm) and (iii) well crystallised spinel Co₃O₄ structures. The volumetric
658 adsorption study has shown that the addition of high amounts of Co (≥ 8.5%) notably
659 decreases the acid character of the Co(x)/HAP catalysts surface. This is explained by the
660 achievement of Co monolayer densities which cover totally the support surface and,
661 thus, minimise its surface acidity. However, the addition of cobalt (1.1≤x≤19.6) to HAP
662 increases by more than twice its surface basic density.

663 The Co(x)/HAP catalysts have been tested in the oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane. Due
664 to their improved textural and structural properties the resulting Co/hydroxyapatite
665 catalysts have proved higher activity compared to bulk Co₃O₄. Moreover, the present

666 study points out the effect of the HAP support on the catalytic stability and the
667 distribution of the reaction products. For instance, the low Co loading catalysts have
668 resulted more selective towards intermediate products (CO and VC). However, high
669 stability and high selectivity to produce CO₂, as deep oxidation product, have been
670 favoured by the Co-rich catalysts which contain the easily reducible Co³⁺ and Co²⁺ ions.
671 The characterisation of the spent catalysts has shown that they have retained a
672 significant amount of chlorine which consists of (i) adsorbed chlorine species on the
673 exposed surface of bulk Co₃O₄ and (ii) a fraction that ion-exchanges hydroxide anions
674 leading to the conversion of the hydroxyapatite into its chlorinated analogue.

675

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681

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689 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

- Table 1 Characterization of the Co(x)/HAP catalysts (Fresh and used in the DCE oxidation)
- Table 2 XPS study of the Co(x)/HAP catalysts (Fresh and used in the DCE oxidation).
- Table 3 Reducibility and surface chemistry of the prepared Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 4 Catalytic data in DCE oxidation over Co(x)/HAP samples.
- Fig. 1 Mesoporous size distribution for the Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP: (A) fresh catalysts and (B) catalysts used in DCE oxidation.
- Fig. 3 (Left) TEM micrographs of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts. (Right) Highlighted visible diffraction plans.
- Fig. 4 FTIR spectra of Co(x)/HAP (A) 4000-400 domain and (B) 1000-500 domain.
- Fig. 5 UV–VIS–NIR spectra of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
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- Fig. 8 Amounts of (a) exchanged cobalt and (b) Co forming Co₃O₄ or Co_xO_y phase on the Co(x)/HAP catalysts, as determined by H₂-TPR, versus overall Co content.
- Fig. 9 DCE conversion and products distribution on the Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 10 Pseudo-first order fit for the DCE oxidation experimental data over the Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 11 Variation of the surface chlorine amounts for the tested Co(x)/HAP catalysts versus non ion-exchanged Co species amounts.
- Fig. 12 DCE oxidation over HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts at 375 °C as a function of time on stream.

Catalysts	Fresh samples								Used samples			
	Ca, ^(a) wt. %	P, ^(a) wt. %	Ca/P	Co, ^(a) wt. %	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _p , nm	Co ₃ O ₄ , nm ^(b)	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _p , nm	Co ₃ O ₄ , nm ^(b)
HAP	33.4	17.2	1.50	0.0	55	0.41	25.8	-	44	0.39	25.9	-
Co(IE)-HAP	29.9	19.6	1.20	1.1	57	0.38	23.4	-	42	0.30	22.5	-
Co(1.1)/HAP	40.5	20.3	1.54	1.1	53	0.39	25.2	-	35	0.23	18.8	-
Co(4.3)/HAP	36.6	18.7	1.51	4.3	46	0.36	25.5	28	43	0.27	20.0	23
Co(8.5)/HAP	29.5	16.3	1.40	8.5	45	0.34	24.6	23	36	0.23	20.5	32
Co(11.2)/HAP	27.3	14.8	1.43	11.2	41	0.32	26.8	25	39	0.26	21.1	28
Co(19.6)/HAP	29.6	15.4	1.48	19.6	41	0.25	21.3	20	29	0.27	26.4	23

(a) Determined by ICP.

(b) Co₃O₄ particle size as determined by XRD.

Table 1

Catalysts	Fresh catalysts						Used catalysts		
	Co 2p _{3/2} , eV	Co 2p _{3/2} satellite, eV	Co/Ca, % (XPS)	Co/Ca, % (ICP)	ΔE , eV ^(a)	S/M ^(b)	Co 2p _{3/2} BE, eV	C, wt.%	Cl, wt.%
HAP	-	-	0.0	0.0	-	-	-	0	6.8
Co(IE)-HAP	782.9	788.9	8.9	1.8	16.4	0.60	782.7	3.0	7.6
Co(1.1)/HAP	781.8	787.6	3.6	1.9	16.0	0.43	782.3	1.8	8.4
Co(4.3)/HAP	780.9	788.7	6.8	8.0	15.0	0.44	782.7	0	9.6
Co(8.5)/HAP	780.6	788.2	9.4	19.6	15.0	0.38	780.9	0	10.0
Co(11.2)/HAP	781.5	788.3	14.9	27.9	15.0	0.39	781.6	0	10.2
Co(19.6)/HAP	781.5	788.8	15.7	45.0	15.0	0.39	781.3	0	9.8

(a) Spin-orbit coupling calculated as: $\Delta E = \text{Co } 2p_{1/2} - \text{Co } 2p_{3/2}$.

(b) Co 2p_{3/2} satellite intensity relative to main photoelectron line.

Table 2

Catalysts	H ₂ -TPR data					Volumetric adsorption studies at 120 °C			
	H ₂ uptake, mmol g ⁻¹	H ₂ /Co	H ₂ uptake, mmol g ⁻¹ (>500°C) ^(a)	IE Co, wt.% ^(b)	H ₂ /Co ^(c) (<500 °C)	Ads NH ₃ , μmol g ⁻¹	Ads NH ₃ , μmol m ⁻²	Ads CO ₂ , μmol g ⁻¹	Ads CO ₂ , μmol m ⁻²
HAP	0	0	0	0	0	80	1.45	12	0.22
Co(IE)-HAP	0.29	1.5	0.29	1.14	0	110	1.93	6	0.11
Co(1.1)/HAP	0.42	2.3	0.17	0.67	3.4	120	2.26	25	0.47
Co(4.3)/HAP	1.19	1.6	0.24	0.94	1.7	100	2.17	25	0.54
Co(8.5)/HAP	2.02	1.4	0.30	1.18	1.4	50	1.11	22	0.49
Co(11.2)/HAP	2.86	1.5	0.34	1.34	1.5	32	0.78	18	0.45
Co(19.6)/HAP	4.68	1.4	0.35	1.37	1.4	40	0.98	20	0.49

(a) Integration of reduction peak at T> 500 °C.

(b) Ion-exchanged Co amount reducible at T> 500 °C as determined from H₂-TPR data.

(c) H₂/Co molar ratio corresponding to the reduction peaks at T<500 °C.

Table 3

	T ₁₀ , °C	T ₅₀ , °C	T ₉₀ , °C	Carbon balance, % ^(a)	CO/CO ₂ ^(a)	Cl ₂ /HCl ^(a)	mol _{DCE} g _{cata} ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ (× 10 ⁸) ^(b)	mol _{DCE} m ⁻² s ⁻¹ (× 10 ¹⁰) ^(b)	Ea ^(c) , kJ mol ⁻¹
HAP	255	335	406	87	5.60	0.002	1.3	2.40	105 ± 1.8
Co(IE)-HAP	303	360	-	72	6.00	0.002	0.4	0.77	108 ± 1.3
Co(1.1)/HAP	293	345	460	78	5.10	0.005	2.1	3.90	75.7 ± 0.7
Co(4.3)/HAP	275	325	413	97	0.05	0.676	3.0	6.60	66.4 ± 0.7
Co(8.5)/HAP	282	355	438	97	0.03	0.845	3.0	6.80	60.7 ± 0.1
Co(11.2)/HAP	275	349	435	89	0.03	0.596	3.0	7.20	62.0 ± 0.3
Co(19.6)/HAP	205	355	417	103	0.01	0.653	2.9	7.10	58.0 ± 0.4
Co ₃ O ₄ [59]	285	380	465	-	-	-	2.6	0.24	55.3 ± 0.4

(a) Values calculated at 500 °C.

(b) Reaction rate calculated at 250 °C.

(c) Activation energy.

Table 4

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Graphical abstract

HIGHLIGHTS – BULLET POINTS

Series of cobalt supported on hydroxyapatite catalysts are synthesised and characterised.

Three types of cobalt species are detected in the prepared catalysts.

The Co catalysts have been successfully tested in the oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane.

The Co(x)/hydroxyapatite catalysts achieve higher activity compared to bulk Co_3O_4 .

The distribution of Co species plays a decisive role in the activity and selectivity.

1 **SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERISATION AND BEHAVIOUR OF**
2 **Co/HYDROXYAPATITE CATALYSTS IN THE OXIDATION OF**
3 **1,2-DICHLOROETHANE**

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23

24 **Abstract**

25 Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite (HAP) loaded with different amounts of cobalt are
26 synthesised and characterised by several techniques including N₂ physisorption, XRD,
27 TEM, H₂-TPR, UV-Visible-NIR DRS, XPS spectroscopy and volumetric adsorption of
28 CO₂ and NH₃ molecules techniques. The Co(x)/HAP catalysts are tested in the
29 oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane. Due to significant enhancement of the textural and
30 structural properties the resulting Co/hydroxyapatite catalysts achieve higher activity
31 compared to bulk Co₃O₄ catalyst confirming the advantage of dispersing cobalt on a
32 relatively high surface area HAP. Hydroxyapatite support shows a high selectivity
33 towards intermediate reaction products; but its activity suffers a significant decay with
34 time due to chlorination. However, high stability and high selectivity towards deep
35 oxidation products are favoured by Co-rich catalysts.

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47 *Keywords:* Hydroxyapatite, Ion-exchanged Co²⁺, Co₃O₄, Surface chemistry, DCE total
48 oxidation

49 **1. Introduction**

50 Due to the increasing awareness of the negative effects of emissions of volatile organic
51 compounds (VOCs) the industrialised countries governments are imposing rigorous
52 legislations. The essential objective is to minimise these emissions under specific
53 standards in order to maintain the equilibrium in the global energy balance and to
54 reduce direct health risks [1-3]. The presence of chlorine atoms in the chemical structure
55 makes them even more resistant to degradation [2-4]. These chlorinated VOCs (Cl-
56 VOCs) are essentially associated with different industrial activities which release a wide
57 variety of molecular compounds. The Cl-VOCs generally include polychloromethanes,
58 polychloroethanes and polychloroethylenes compounds which possess high volatility
59 and strong resistance to destruction [2-5].

60 Though a number of studies dealing with remediation technologies for removal and
61 decomposition of Cl-VOCs are presently available [6-10], thermal incineration is
62 considered by far the most effective strategies [2,7]. However, it requires high operation
63 temperatures ($>700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), thereby increasing the processing cost and NO_x emissions. To
64 overcome these drawbacks the catalytic oxidation appears to be a good alternative
65 allowing lower operating temperatures and better control of the reaction products [11-
66 18]. Thus, the synthesis of active and stable catalysts for Cl-VOCs oxidation at low
67 temperature and with high selectivity towards complete oxidation products, i.e. CO_2 ,
68 H_2O and HCl/Cl_2 is receiving increasing attention in the literature [11-18].

69 A considerable number of suitable catalytic systems, including noble metals [19-21] and
70 transition metals [11, 12, 14, 22, 23, 24], have been investigated for total oxidation of
71 chlorinated compounds. As major drawbacks of expensive noble metals are adsorption
72 of chlorine species on the active surface and sintering of the metal active sites at high
73 temperatures [14]. Transition metal oxides (V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Nb, and Mo)

74 appear as a good alternative to noble metal catalysts because of their low cost and their
75 resistance to chlorine poisoning [2, 11, 12, 14, 24].

76 Despite their high activity in the oxidation of hydrocarbons and carbon monoxide cobalt
77 catalysts have scarcely attracted attention concerning their applicability in the removal
78 of chlorinated volatile compounds. The few available investigations dealing with this
79 formulation demonstrated their promising performance for Cl-VOCs removal [11, 12,
80 14]. We previously studied the catalytic performance of a series of bulk Co_3O_4 catalysts
81 prepared by a variety of routes in the gas-phase oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane [11],
82 resulting in considerably higher activity and stability than supported noble metals (Pt,
83 Pd), protonic zeolites, and Ce/Zr and Mn/Zr mixed oxides. This catalytic performance
84 of bulk Co_3O_4 catalysts was related to the oxygen mobility and the acid character of
85 surface active sites. In this sense, Cai et al. [14] studied the influence of modifying the
86 Co_3O_4 structure, by incorporation of small amount of Mn, on the catalytic activity in the
87 oxidation of 1,2-dichlorobenzene. They reported that Mn species retarded the oxygen
88 mobility of surface active oxygen and increased Co^{2+} concentration which had a
89 positive effect on activity, selectivity and stability of $\text{Mn}_x\text{Co}_{3-x}\text{O}_4$ catalyst.

90 Though less detailed and numerous, some papers dedicated to this environmental
91 application have also dealt with the textural properties improvement of Co_3O_4 by means
92 of its dispersion on conventional supports (alumina, zeolite, SiO_2). However, it was
93 proved that this route significantly reduces the activity due to the formation of inactive
94 Co species. For example, Chintawar et al. [25] reported that Co loaded zeolite Y and
95 alumina catalysts were not feasible for the complete catalytic oxidation of chlorinated
96 ethylenes. Generally, in the case of cobalt alumina supported catalysts, an interaction
97 between cobalt oxide and catalyst support could result in incorporation of some
98 Al^{3+} ions into Co_3O_4 spinel matrix resulting in $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{Co}^{3+}_{2-x}\text{Al}_x\text{O}_4$ mixed spinels which

99 would hinder the reduction of Co_3O_4 particles and their oxygen mobility capacity [25,
100 26].

101 Hydroxyapatite, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ (HAP), has been intensively investigated as porous
102 support [27-34]. The interest was justified by the presence of phosphate groups which
103 stabilise the structure of active sites and allow the tuning of acid-base properties by
104 varying the calcium/phosphorus ratio. Moreover, the ability of hydroxyapatite to
105 undergo cation and anion exchanges, due to the presence of two types of zeolite-like
106 channels, leads to modulate its chemical properties without damaging its typical
107 hexagonal structure [28]. These characteristics confer to hydroxyapatite catalysts the
108 generation of new synergic metal-support interactions which could improve their
109 catalytic activity [35-41]. Particularly Moffat's group [35, 40] found promising results
110 on the destruction of chlorinated compounds over this type of catalysts.

111 The aim of this work is the investigation of the textural, structural, surface chemistry
112 and catalytic behaviour of a series of calcium deficient hydroxyapatite-supported cobalt
113 samples in the total oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE), selected as one of the most
114 important chlorinated pollutants emitted in gaseous industrial waste streams [3, 11]. The
115 choice of HAP was made because of the possibility of the control of the Co-support
116 interaction. In this sense, due to its low capacity to exchange Co^{2+} ions (<1.4%) it was
117 expected that this might limit the aforementioned loss of Co active phase compared to
118 conventional supports. The characterisation of the prepared samples involved a wide
119 number of techniques including BET, TEM, XRD, H_2 -TPR, FTIR, UV-visible-NIR
120 DRS, XPS spectroscopy and volumetric adsorption of NH_3 and CO_2 as well-known
121 probe molecules for acid and basic sites, respectively. Cobalt ion-exchanged
122 hydroxyapatite catalyst is also prepared in order to be used as reference. To the best of

123 our knowledge, the applicability of these catalytic materials in the gas-phase oxidation
124 of DCE reaction has not been yet investigated.

125

126 **2. Experimental**

127 **2.1. Preparation of the catalysts**

128 Hydroxyapatite support (HAP) was synthesised adding dropwise a boiling aqueous
129 solution of calcium nitrate to a solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$. The precipitate was re-
130 dissolved in a nitric acid solution and neutralised with ammonia at pH 10. The resulting
131 mixture was maintained under stirring at 80 °C for 16 h. After filtration, the recovered
132 solid was thoroughly washed with purified water, then dried at 120 °C and finally
133 calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

134 Cobalt loaded HAP catalysts were prepared by incipient wetness impregnation using
135 solutions containing varying amounts of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The impregnated samples
136 were dried in air at 110 °C for 12 h and subsequently calcined for 4 h, at 500 °C. The
137 resulting samples will be hereafter referred as $\text{Co}(x)/\text{HAP}$. The loaded amount of cobalt
138 was represented by 'x' and it corresponded to the actual Co weight percentage in the
139 catalyst. The final chemical composition was confirmed by means of ICP analysis.

140 An ion-exchanged sample, $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, was also prepared at room temperature by
141 introducing 10 g of HAP into 1000 cm^3 of aqueous solution containing $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
142 (2g). After stirring for 24 h the solid recovered after filtration was washed, dried at 120
143 °C and finally calcined at 500 °C.

144

145 **2.2. Characterisation techniques**

146 The volumetric N_2 adsorption at -196 °C was performed on an automatic apparatus
147 Micromeritics, model TRISTAR II 3020 apparatus. The pre-treatments applied to the

148 samples consisted of a cleaning, at 300 °C (overnight), under nitrogen flow. The
149 specific areas of the samples were determined in line with the standard BET procedure,
150 using nitrogen adsorption taken in the relative equilibrium pressure interval of 0.03-0.3.
151 X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were conducted on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray
152 diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) and Ni filter. The X-ray tube was
153 operated at 40 kV and 40 mA. The samples were scanned between 10° and 100° (2θ),
154 and the X-ray diffraction line positions were determined with a step size of 0.01° and a
155 counting time of 2.5 s per step. Phase identification was conducted by comparison with
156 JCPDS database cards. From the XRD data, the degree of crystallinity of the
157 synthesised HAP was estimated using the following equation (1) [42]:

$$158 \quad d_c = \left(\frac{K}{B_{(002)}} \right)^3 \quad (1)$$

159 where d_c is the degree of crystallinity, B_{002} is full width at half maximum (°) of
160 reflection (002) and K is a characteristic constant for HAP structures found equal to
161 0.24. Moreover, the Co_3O_4 crystallite size was calculated by Scherrer equation, using
162 Co_3O_4 (311) ($2\theta = 37.1^\circ$) diffraction line broadening.

163 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) absorption spectra were recorded in the
164 400-4000 cm^{-1} range with a Cary 600 Series FTIR spectrometer using disks of samples
165 diluted in KBr. The oxidation states and the coordination of Co were evaluated by
166 diffuse reflectance UV-vis spectroscopy (UV-Visible-NIR DRS) with a UV-vis-NIR
167 Cary 5000 apparatus coupled to Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500 within a range of
168 200–2500 nm.

169 XPS spectra were recorded on a Phoibos 150 1D-DLD analysis system from Specs,
170 with monochromatic Al K α radiation (1486.6 eV). The hemispheric photoelectron
171 analyser worked with a pass energy of 40 eV for survey scan and 20 eV for detail scan.

172 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations were carried out with a Philips
173 CM200 transmission electron microscope equipped with LaB₆ filament operating at
174 200 kV. The sample powder was dispersed in ethanol, dropped on copper grids, coated
175 with lacey carbon film, and evaporated at room temperature.

176 Redox behaviour was examined by temperature-programmed reduction (H₂-TPR) on a
177 Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument. Firstly, all the samples were pre-treated in
178 an oxygen stream (5%O₂/He) at 400 °C for 1 h and then cooled to room temperature.
179 The reducing gas used in all experiments was 5%H₂/Ar, with a flow rate of 50 cm³ min⁻¹
180 ¹. The temperature range explored was from room temperature to 1000 °C, with a
181 heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. This temperature was maintained for 30 min. The water
182 produced by reduction was trapped in a cold trap, and the consumption of H₂ was
183 quantitatively measured by time integration of the TPR profiles.

184 The acid/base properties of the catalysts were determined by NH₃-pulse/CO₂-pulse
185 experiments carried out at 120 °C. The samples were submitted to a pre-treatment
186 routine consisting of heating in a flow of 5%O₂/He, at 500 °C (30 min), and cooling
187 down to 120 °C in a flow of He. NH₃ or CO₂ pulses were then injected in a He carrier
188 over the sample during 30 s, with a time interval between pulses of 10 min. The NH₃ or
189 CO₂ signal was online analysed online with an automatic apparatus Micromeritics,
190 AutoChem 2920 instrument, equipped with thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

191

192 **2.3. Catalytic tests**

193 Catalytic tests were performed in a bench-scale fixed bed reactor operated at
194 atmospheric pressure. The reactor was made of quartz with an internal diameter of
195 10 mm and a height of 300 mm, in which the temperature is controlled with a
196 thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. Typically 0.85 g of catalyst in powdered form

197 (0.3–0.5 mm) was loaded. The reaction feed consisted of 1000 ppm of DCE in dry air
198 with a total gas flow of $500 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ($15,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$). It should be noted that the
199 experimental conditions employed in this work were chosen to meet the criteria to
200 ensure the absence of the mass and heat transfer limitations, as described elsewhere
201 [11]. Catalytic activity was measured over the range 150-500 °C and conversion data
202 were calculated by the difference between inlet and outlet concentrations. Conversion
203 measurements and product profiles were taken at steady state, typically after 30 minutes
204 on stream.

205 The feed and effluent streams were analysed using an on-line 7980A Agilent
206 Technologies gas chromatograph equipped with a thermal conductivity (CO and CO₂)
207 and an electron capture detector (chlorinated hydrocarbons). Analysis of HCl and
208 Cl₂ was carried out by means of ion selective electrode and titration, respectively.
209 Further details on analytical procedures can be found elsewhere [11]. On basis of the
210 concentrations [Ci] at the outlet of the reactor, product yields (CO₂, CO, vinyl chloride
211 (VC: C₂H₃Cl), HCl and Cl₂) were calculated, according to the following equations:

$$212 \quad S_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{[\text{CO}_2]}{2[\text{VC}] + [\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (2)$$

$$213 \quad S_{\text{CO}} = \frac{[\text{CO}]}{2[\text{VC}] + [\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (3)$$

$$214 \quad S_{\text{VC}} = \frac{2[\text{VC}]}{2[\text{VC}] + [\text{CO}_2] + [\text{CO}]} \quad (4)$$

$$215 \quad S_{\text{HCl}} = \frac{[\text{HCl}]}{2[\text{Cl}_2] + [\text{CV}] + [\text{HCl}]} \quad (5)$$

$$216 \quad S_{\text{Cl}_2} = \frac{2[\text{Cl}_2]}{2[\text{Cl}_2] + [\text{CV}] + [\text{HCl}]} \quad (6)$$

217 **3. Results and discussion**

218 **3.1. Characterisation of the samples**

219 **3.1.1. Chemical analysis**

220 Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the HAP-supported cobalt catalyst along
221 with that of the bare support. Judging from the obtained results, the synthesised support
222 consists of a calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite with Ca/P molar ratio equal to 1.50,
223 lower than the 1.67 expected for a stoichiometric hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$).
224 According to many authors this non-stoichiometry can be explained by loss of Ca^{2+}
225 ions, which is corrected by insertion of H^+ ions at the expense of hydroxyl groups to
226 ensure electroneutrality [43-44]. Hence, the general formula of these calcium deficient
227 hydroxyapatite can be denoted as $\text{Ca}_{10-z}(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$ where $0 < z \leq 1$. The
228 Ca/P ratio corresponding to Co(IE)-HAP sample, prepared by ion-exchange method, is
229 relatively lower (1.20), thereby suggesting that the substituted Ca^{2+} ions were lixiviated
230 during the filtration process. By contrast, for the five impregnated Co(x)/HAP samples,
231 the Ca/P ratio is quite similar (about 1.5) which evidenced no further loss of calcium.
232 On the other hand, the cobalt loadings are found to be ranged between 1.1-19.6wt.%
233 (Table 1). This wide range could allow us to study the evolution of the samples
234 properties, with the progressive increase of Co surface density, from sub-monolayer to
235 over-monolayer densities. Note that the theoretical monolayer estimation
236 (corresponding to a cobalt loading of 8.1wt.%) is made in accordance with that
237 proposed for the monolayer of cobalt supported on alumina as to reach a surface density
238 of 16 Co atoms nm^{-2} [45].

239

240 **3.1.2. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

241 The experimental N₂ physisorption isotherms for Co(x)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts
242 (not shown) and the data reported in Table 1 show that the isotherms were characteristic
243 of mesoporous materials exhibiting IV-type according to the IUPAC classification. Fig.

244 1 shows the pore size distributions for all the prepared catalysts. The pore size
245 distribution corresponding to HAP support and the Co(x)/HAP catalysts ($x \leq 11.2\text{wt.}\%$)
246 show a broad unimodal distribution centred at approximately 30 nm (Fig. 1). However,
247 at high Co loading (19.6wt.%) a slight shift of the distribution peak towards lower
248 values (25 nm) is observed. On the other hand, the increased addition of cobalt to HAP
249 produces a progressive drop in its specific surface area (up to 25%) and pore volume
250 (up to 39%). For instance, the specific surface area of the resultant catalysts
251 significantly decreases from $55 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for the HAP bare support to $41 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for
252 Co(11.2)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts.

253

254 **3.1.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

255 The Co(x)/HAP catalysts were characterised by means of X-ray powder diffraction in
256 order to investigate their structural properties. The diffractogram of the HAP support
257 calcined at 500 °C, Fig. 2A, is identical to the hexagonal hydroxyapatite structure
258 presenting a $P6_3/m$ space group (JCPDS: 74-0565). Moreover, the degree of
259 crystallinity of the prepared HAP is estimated to be around 0.8. This is in agreement
260 with an earlier study reporting that the calcination of apatite materials at or above 500
261 °C could lead to a crystallinity degree of about 0.7-0.8 [46]. It should be pointed out that
262 the presence of hydroxyapatite as unique phase, on the HAP diffractogram, confirms
263 that its structure is tolerant to deviation from the stoichiometry. Yet, the formation of β -
264 tricalcium phosphate as a product of hydroxyapatite decomposition is not expected after
265 calcination at 500 °C [44].

266 The diffractograms of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts show no lines
267 corresponding to cobalt oxides crystals (Fig. 2A) probably because of their high
268 dispersion and/or the fact that the formed crystallites are smaller than their detection

269 limit. With these limitations spectroscopic measurements could present an alternative
270 option to characterise these samples because well-resolved spectra could be obtained
271 with small Co loadings. At higher Co concentration, 4.3-19.6%, two additional typical
272 peaks belonging to Co_3O_4 spinel structure, JCPDS 76-1802, appeared at $2\theta = 31.6^\circ$ and
273 37.1° (Fig. 2A). Their intensity increases, as expected, with cobalt loading. Table 1 also
274 reports the Co_3O_4 crystal size calculated by Scherrer equation. The average size of the
275 Co_3O_4 particles is around 24-32 nm on the $\text{Co}(x)/\text{HAP}$ catalysts ($x \geq 4.3\%$).

276

277 **3.1.4. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

278 The catalysts with low Co loadings, $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, were investigated
279 by TEM in order to estimate the Co species particle sizes, not detected by XRD. The
280 micrographs of the two samples show some differences in morphology. On the $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-}$
281 HAP catalyst some scratched dark areas and zones presenting low contrast are observed.
282 The presence of the former may be related with well crystallised HAP areas where some
283 of its reticular planes form channels in which the Co ions are incorporated. The
284 measured distance between visible diffraction plans is approximately 0.8 nm.
285 Examination of $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ micrograph reveals the presence of similar areas observed
286 on the $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$ catalyst together with small Co particles, ranged between 6-10 nm,
287 which have a quasi spherical shape. Since the two samples are loaded with the same
288 amount of Co, 1.1wt.%, these observations are probably related with the method used
289 for the preparation of each catalyst and the subsequent distribution of formed Co
290 species. As will be shown later, the apparition of Co species with relatively high particle
291 sizes on the impregnated sample ($\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$) compared to $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, prepared by
292 ion exchange method, may be explained by the growth of some Co species on the
293 support surface.

294 **3.1.5. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)**

295 FTIR spectroscopy is commonly used to complete the structural characterisation of
296 apatite materials made by means of XRD techniques. The objective is essentially to
297 confirm the presence of hydroxyls and phosphate groups and the presence or the
298 absence of some derived phosphate groups like $(\text{HPO}_4)^{2-}$ anions. Fig. 4 includes the
299 FTIR spectra for HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts. The recorded spectrum corresponding
300 to HAP bare support is characteristic of non-stoichiometric hydroxyapatite structures
301 (Fig. 4). The five bands centred at 566, 602, 960, 1035 and 1095 cm^{-1} are assigned to
302 different vibration modes of P-O bonds in the $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ groups [27-28, 47]. Moreover, the
303 vibration of hydroxyls groups hosted by the apatite framework is evidenced by the
304 presence of a small sharp band at 3575 cm^{-1} and a more intense feature at 630 cm^{-1} . It
305 should be noted that, as expected, in agreement with the ICP results, the spectrum of
306 HAP sample presents a band around 875 cm^{-1} which attests the presence of $(\text{HPO}_4)^{2-}$
307 ions; typical of calcium deficient hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10-z}(\text{HPO}_4)_z(\text{PO}_4)_{6-z}(\text{OH})_{2-z}$). The
308 HAP spectrum also shows additional bands attributed to adsorbed water (1630 and 3400
309 cm^{-1}) and carbonates (1385 cm^{-1}) [27-28, 48].

310 It should be noted that no significant changes are detected on the Co(IE)-HAP spectrum
311 compared with the bare support. However, the samples prepared by impregnation
312 displayed a new band at 663 cm^{-1} which increases with the Co loading (Fig. 4). The
313 signal is attributed to the Co-O stretching vibration characteristic of spinel Co_3O_4 [48-
314 51]. Moreover, new shoulders appear at higher Co loading which affected the
315 absorption of the water molecule vibrations in the 3200-3600 cm^{-1} range. Jones et al.
316 [52] reported that this effect could indicate the presence of water coordinated to the
317 metal ion. By contrast, at low loading the Co ion-exchanged is the dominant Co species
318 which does not significantly disturb the vibrations of adsorbed water molecules.

319 3.1.6. UV-Visible-NIR diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-Visible-NIR DRS)

320 Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was used to study the symmetry and the oxidation
321 state of cobalt species dispersed on the HAP support. It is known that, in normal Co_3O_4
322 spinel structure, the Co^{2+} ions ($3d^7$) occupy tetrahedral coordination (Td) while the Co^{3+}
323 ions ($3d^6$) host an octahedral surrounding (Oh). The optical spectra of these Co species
324 are generally composed of i) three spin allowed d-d transitions in the visible region
325 corresponding to Co^{3+} Oh symmetry and ii) three transitions in the visible and NIR
326 regions for the Co^{2+} Td coordination. Moreover, the interaction between the two Co
327 sites can produce additional absorption bands due to metal to metal charge transfer
328 distributed between the visible and NIR regions.

329 Fig. 5 displays the UV-visible-NIR spectra for the prepared $\text{Co}(x)/\text{HAP}$ samples. A
330 spectrum of bulk Co_3O_4 , prepared by decomposition of cobalt nitrate at 500°C , is also
331 analysed for comparison. The HAP spectrum exhibits absorption bands in the NIR
332 region related to surface hydroxyls groups, 1300-1500 nm, and another one assigned to
333 structural OH groups, 1900-2100 nm (Fig. 5) [27,28]. In the UV region, a band around
334 200 nm, ascribed to $\text{O}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Ca}^{2+}$ charge transfers [27,28], is also observed.

335 The spectrum of the ion-exchanged sample, $\text{Co}(\text{IE})\text{-HAP}$, is characterised by the
336 presence of three d-d transitions bands between 520-630 nm, in the visible region, and a
337 broad band extended in the NIR domain (1000-1800 nm) (Fig. 5). Similar spectra were
338 obtained in previous works dealing with the characterisation of cobalt at cation
339 exchange sites. For instance, in their study on spectroscopy and coordination chemistry
340 of cobalt in molecular sieves Verberckmoes et al. [53] reported that these absorptions
341 could be assigned to ν_3 (${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$) and ν_1 (${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$) transitions of the
342 octahedral Co^{2+} located in cation exchange sites. From these results we can conclude

343 that, in Co(IE)-HAP sample, the exchanged Co^{2+} species are probably hosted by
344 octahedral sites.

345 On the other hand, the impregnated samples spectra show a striking similarity with the
346 bulk Co_3O_4 spectrum (Fig. 5). The absorption bands centred at 1200-1500 nm and 670
347 nm are attributed to ν_1 (${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{F})$) and ν_2 (${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P})$) transitions, respectively,
348 which correspond to tetrahedral Co^{2+} [54]. Likewise, the presence of octahedral Co^{3+}
349 ions is evidenced by their characteristic d-d transitions bands, centred at 750 nm and
350 350-460 nm, associated with ν_1 (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{1g}$) and ν_2 (${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{T}_{2g}$), respectively [54]. It
351 is relevant to highlight that the latter shifts towards the UV domain with Co loading
352 (from 460 nm for Co(1.1)/HAP to 350 nm for the catalysts with higher Co loading).
353 This suggests the growth of tridimensional and well crystallised Co_3O_4 on these Co-rich
354 samples. By contrast, despite the presence of Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} ions on the Co(1.1)/HAP
355 sample its spectrum shows a difference respect to those corresponding to
356 Co($4.5 \leq x \leq 19.6$)/HAP. Moreover, it was observed that the color turned from grey for the
357 Co(1.1)/HAP to black for the Co($4.5 \leq x \leq 19.6$)/HAP catalysts. According to earlier
358 studies [55], these observations clearly indicate that on the Co(1.1)/HAP catalyst the Co
359 could form Co_xO_y clusters composed of a mixture of octahedral Co^{3+} and tetrahedral
360 Co^{2+} . These can be considered as precursors of Co_3O_4 nanocrystals. These results are in
361 agreement with the findings from TEM and XRD analyses. The Co species particles
362 (<10 nm) found on the Co(1.1)/HAP are much smaller than those corresponding to
363 Co($4.5 \leq x \leq 19.6$)/HAP catalysts, in the 23-32 nm range. It is worth mentioning that the
364 presence of exchanged Co^{2+} species in the impregnated Co(x)/HAP samples can not be
365 ruled out since their absorption bands may overlap with those of spinel Co_3O_4 structure.

366

367 **3.1.7. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)**

368 The influence of the Co content on the surface distribution of cobalt species has been
369 investigated by means of XPS techniques. Fig. 6 and Table 2 summarise the
370 corresponding results. The Co 2p XPS spectra for all the Co(x)/HAP samples have been
371 processed while maintaining the Co 2p_{3/2}/Co 2p_{1/2} area ratio at approximately 2 (Fig. 6).
372 The Co 2p_{3/2} spectra consist of a main photoemission peak (M) located at a binding
373 energy (BE) in the range of 780.8-783 eV and a satellite peak (S) attributed to a shake-
374 up process, appearing at approximately 6-8 eV higher BE.

375 In the Co 2p_{3/2} region, the XPS profile for the Co(IE)-HAP catalyst exhibits two peaks,
376 centred at 783.1 and 788.9 eV, attributed to Co²⁺ and its typical shake-up satellite peak,
377 respectively. As expected, the impregnation of cobalt onto the HAP surface slightly
378 shifts the Co 2p_{3/2} main peak position to lower BE, compared to Co(IE)-HAP sample,
379 suggesting the near surface enrichment with Co³⁺ ions (Fig. 6 and Table 2) [54]. The
380 main Co 2p_{3/2} peak corresponding to Co(8.5)/HAP, Co(11.2)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP
381 tend to split into two signals corresponding to two distinct contributions. The first one
382 centred at 780.8 eV is attributed to Co³⁺ ions while the shoulder situated at 783.2±0.2 eV
383 is assigned to Co²⁺ species. These results are in good agreement with the FTIR and DRS
384 studies and clearly corroborated the previous findings by evidencing the formation of
385 Co₃O₄ crystals in the impregnated Co(x≥4.3)/HAP samples. This conclusion is also
386 supported by the spin-orbit splitting (ΔE) and S/M ratio values reported in Table 2.
387 Indeed, the observed decrease in these two parameters with increasing Co content
388 suggests the evolution towards a major contribution of Co³⁺ ions and, then, the
389 deposition of spinel Co₃O₄ structure [54]. For instance, the measured ΔE decreases from
390 16.4 eV for Co(IE)-HAP catalyst to 15 eV for Co(8.5)/HAP Co(11.2)/HAP and
391 Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts. Likewise, the calculated S/M values decrease from 0.60 for
392 Co(IE)-HAP to 0.39 for Co(11.2)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts.

393 Table 2 also offers a comparison between the Co/Ca molar ratios calculated from the
394 XPS and ICP data. When comparing the Co/Ca molar ratio values of Co(IE)-HAP and
395 Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts, having the same Co content (1.1wt.%) but prepared by different
396 methods, it is observed that it is higher in the ion-exchanged sample. This higher Co/Ca
397 ratio value can be explained by the substitution of Ca^{2+} ions lixiviated during the
398 filtration process, by Co^{2+} ions.

399

400 **3.1.8. Temperature programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR)**

401 The H_2 -TPR experiments were performed in order to investigate the reducibility of
402 different Co species present in the Co(x)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts. To our
403 knowledge, similar H_2 -TPR study, concerning the Co/HAP materials, has not been yet
404 published. Fig. 7 displays the H_2 -TPR profiles of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP for
405 different Co loadings. Table 3 reports the quantitative data calculated from the
406 integration of the resulted reduction peaks. Fig. 7 shows that no reduction peak was
407 found on the HAP bare support. The diagram of Co(IE)-HAP sample shows a broad
408 reduction peak at high temperature (>500 °C), associated with the reduction of
409 exchanged Co^{2+} ions. As shown in Table 3, the integration of this reduction peak gives a
410 value of H_2 consumption of 0.29 mmol g^{-1} (1.14% Co^{2+}). This is consistent with our
411 above mentioned proposal (the presence of exchanged Co^{2+} as unique Co phase) since it
412 was close to the overall Co content (1.1%) determined by ICP.

413 Fig.7 also shows the H_2 -TPR traces corresponding to Co(x)/HAP impregnated catalysts.

414 In this series of catalysts, the reduction profiles are quite similar. Hence, they are
415 characterised by the presence of two typical reduction peaks of bulk Co_3O_4 , in the 250-
416 500 °C temperature range, and a reduction peak due to the exchanged Co^{2+} ions at high
417 temperatures (>500 °C). The Co_3O_4 reduction process takes place realised through two

418 steps consisting of the reduction of Co^{3+} ions to Co^{2+} (peak around 300-330 °C)
419 accompanied by much more intense reduction peak due to the reduction of Co^{2+} ions to
420 metallic cobalt (375-430 °C) [11]. As revealed by the sixth column data reported in
421 Table 3, the H_2/Co molar ratio values (1.4-1.5) corresponding to the low reduction
422 peaks temperatures (<500 °C) for $\text{Co}(8.5 \leq x \leq 19.6)/\text{HAP}$ catalysts are close to 1.33,
423 expected for stoichiometric Co_3O_4 . By contrast, for the $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ sample this value
424 is significantly higher (3.4) suggesting the deposition of non-stoichiometric Co_3O_4 . The
425 latter is in good agreement with our characterisation results, discussed above, which
426 suggested the formation of Co_xO_y clusters composed of a mixture of octahedral Co^{3+}
427 and tetrahedral Co^{2+} . Fig. 8 reports the relationship between the overall Co content
428 determined by ICP and the contribution of the two phases of Co, ion-exchanged and
429 deposited as Co_3O_4 or Co_xO_y , calculated from the integration of the corresponding
430 reduction peaks. The amount of Co ion-exchanged species increases slowly with the Co
431 loading from 0.67% on $\text{Co}(1.1)/\text{HAP}$ up to 1.34%, on the $\text{Co}(11.2)/\text{HAP}$ catalyst, above
432 which remains unchanged with Co loading. However, the contribution of Co spread as
433 Co_3O_4 or Co_xO_y over the carrier linearly increases with Co loading.

434

435 **3.1.9. Volumetric adsorption studies**

436 The acid-base properties of the prepared catalysts were investigated by means of
437 volumetric adsorption techniques. NH_3 and CO_2 were used as probe molecules to
438 determine the acid and basic surface densities, respectively. Twenty consecutive pulses
439 at 120 °C separated by 10 min evacuation treatment at the same temperature were
440 recorded. In general, the first pulses of reactive gas are sufficient to reach the maximum
441 adsorption capacity of the samples. Then, the adsorption data are determined from the

442 difference between the first and second experimental pulses. The corresponding data are
443 included in Table 3.

444 Hence, the surface density for NH₃ adsorption sites on HAP support is 1.45 μmol m⁻²
445 whereas it does not adsorb more than 0.22 μmol m⁻² of CO₂. This difference is
446 explained by the calcium deficiency of the support which leads to a surface with a
447 notable acidic character [27-28]. This is why in the case of the Co(IE)-HAP sample,
448 presenting a substitution of Ca²⁺ by Co²⁺ ions, the density of surface acidity is, even
449 more, enhanced (1.93 μmol m⁻²) at the expense of the surface basicity (0.11 μmol m⁻²).

450 Though not proceeding via analogous pathway the impregnation of cobalt onto the HAP
451 surface influences dramatically the amount of the adsorbed NH₃ and CO₂. According
452 to Table 3, the surface density of adsorbed CO₂ on the support, 0.22 μmol m⁻², is much
453 smaller than that determined for Co(x)/HAP, 0.45-0.54 μmol m⁻². Likewise, the surface
454 acidity slightly increases with the addition of small amounts of Co (≤ 4.3%), but it
455 notably decreases for the samples with high Co loadings (≥ 8.5%). For example the
456 surface density of adsorbed NH₃ results in 2.26 μmol m⁻² for Co(1.1)/HAP while around
457 1.11 μmol m⁻² in the case of the Co(8.5)/HAP catalyst. This drastic change in the acid
458 character on the Co(x)/HAP catalysts can be explained by the achievement of Co
459 monolayer densities which cover totally the support surface and, then, minimise their
460 surface acidity. However, for all the Co(x)/HAP catalysts, the surface basicity becomes
461 twice compared to bare HAP support.

462

463 **3.2. Catalytic behaviour in the oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE)**

464 The DCE oxidation reaction was examined over the calcined catalysts in the
465 temperature window between 150 and 500 °C, by sequentially increasing the reaction
466 temperature with 25 °C intervals (light-off curves). Fig. 9A displays the evolution of

467 DCE conversion (X_{DCE}) over the Co(x)/HAP catalysts versus reaction temperature.
468 With the reactor filled up with pure HAP the reaction begins around 200 °C and
469 increased slowly up to 300 °C. Then it started to increase rapidly with reaction
470 temperature. At 450 °C, the DCE conversion is close to 100%. Over the Co(IE)-HAP
471 ion-exchanged catalyst the reaction ignition starts at 275 °C and the conversion
472 increases slowly with the temperature, but it does not exceed 83% at 500 °C. The shape
473 of activity traces for Co(x)/HAP impregnated catalysts is almost similar compared to
474 that of HAP support. Table 4 compares the obtained results in terms of temperatures at
475 which the DCE conversion reached 10 (T_{10}), 50 (T_{50}), and 90% (T_{90}). Some recently
476 published results for a bulk Co_3O_4 oxide ($11 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) are used as reference for
477 comparison [59]. Data in Table 4 show that the catalytic activity, on the basis of T_{50}
478 values, follows this trend: Co(4.3)/HAP (325 °C) > HAP (335 °C) > Co(1.1)/HAP (345
479 °C) > Co(11.2)/HAP > Co(8.5)/HAP ~ Co(19.6)/HAP > Co(IE)-HAP (360 °C) > Co_3O_4
480 (380 °C). This tendency proves the comparable potential of HAP support in comparison
481 with the cobalt catalysts to decompose DCE. Table 4 also shows activity data referred to
482 1 g of catalyst and 1 m^2 of BET surface area. On the HAP sample the specific catalytic
483 activity is around $2.4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ suggesting that Ca-deficient hydroxyapatite
484 is not an inert support when applied in DCE oxidation reaction. For the series of
485 Co(x)/HAP impregnated catalysts the specific catalytic activity value seems to increase
486 with the cobalt loading from 3.9×10^{-10} for Co(1.1)/HAP to $7.1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2}$
487 s^{-1} for Co(11.2)/HAP catalyst but it remains almost constant for the catalyst with the
488 highest copper loading (19.6%). It is worth outlining that the Co(IE)-HAP catalyst
489 shows the lowest activity ($0.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) with respect to the Co(x)/HAP
490 catalysts. Besides, when compared to the low specific activity of pure Co_3O_4 (0.24
491 $\times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}_{\text{DCE}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) the notable improved textural and structural properties of the

492 resulting Co/hydroxyapatite catalysts make them advantageously more active than the
493 bulk spinel.

494 Table 4 summarises the values of the apparent activation energy (E_a) for the Co(x)/HAP
495 catalysts. The corresponding calculations are made assuming a first order reaction and a
496 linear correlation is obtained between $\ln[-\ln(1-X_{DCE})]$ and $1/T$ (Fig. 10). The analysis of
497 the obtained results shows that relatively high activation energy values, 105-108 kJ mol^{-1}
498 ¹, are obtained on the HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts. However, the E_a values decrease
499 significantly with the supported cobalt phases to reach values about 58-62 kJ mol^{-1} over
500 Co($x \geq 8.3\%$), close to those exhibited by the bulk Co_3O_4 prepared by different routes
501 (53-56 kJ mol^{-1}) [59].

502

503 **3.3. Structure-activity-selectivity relationships**

504 In their study on the methanol oxidation reaction over Co/hydroxyapatite Aellach et al.
505 [37] concluded that the redox properties of Co_3O_4 and acid properties of the apatite
506 support led to a very efficient catalyst compared to bulk Co_3O_4 . Moreover, the presence
507 of surface cationic vacancies on the Ca-deficient hydroxyapatite can improve the
508 catalytic activity. This might explain the low activity of our Co(IE)-HAP catalyst. The
509 characterization of the latter has confirmed the presence of hardly reducible Co^{2+} (ion-
510 exchanged) as unique Co phase. Then, the poor performance can be related to an
511 inactivity of this Co species and the absence of surface cationic vacancies which are
512 occupied by the Co^{2+} ions. The relatively higher activity of HAP, compared to that of
513 Co(IE)-HAP, can support our claim; especially, the former contains cation vacancies
514 due to its Ca-deficiency.

515 On the other hand, the increase of the activity over the Co(x)/HAP samples with the
516 increase of Co loadings can be explained by the surface Co_3O_4 enrichment which

517 contains easily reducible Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} species. This is in good agreement with the
518 relatively comparable activation energy determined on the Co-rich samples and bulk
519 Co_3O_4 (Table 4). This suggests that the activity is controlled by similar near surface
520 composition, characterised by an abundance of Co_3O_4 crystals. On pure Co_3O_4 the
521 surface density of Co sites is certainly larger than that for Co(x)/HAP supported
522 samples; however, this difference is overcompensated by their much higher surface area
523 and their relatively low Co_3O_4 crystal size (20-25 nm) compared with bulk Co_3O_4 (38
524 nm).

525 Figs. 9 (B, C, D, E and F) show the concentration-temperature profiles of the main
526 oxidation products (CO_2 , CO, VC, HCl and Cl_2 , respectively). Table 4 also includes the
527 carbon balance, CO/ CO_2 and Cl_2 /HCl ratios calculated at 500 °C for each tested
528 catalyst. The formation of CO_2 , as deep DCE oxidation (7) product, seems to be
529 affected by the Co loading and, then, the Co species lying on the surface (Fig. 9B).

531 For the catalysts with Co contents lower than 4.3% the CO_2 production does not exceed
532 100 ppm whereas it notably increased over the high Co loading catalysts ($x \geq 4.3\%$). For
533 instance, on the Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst the CO_2 concentration reaches a maximum of
534 2000 ppm at 500 °C and over Co(4.3)/HAP 1700 ppm of CO_2 is produced at 500 °C. It
535 could be concluded that, in agreement with our characterisation results, formation of
536 CO_2 as a product of the DCE total oxidation should mainly involve the Co_3O_4 species
537 (Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} ions) deposited on the support surface which are easily reducible as
538 reported in H_2 -TPR section. Conversely, the yield of CO is markedly favoured (Fig. 9C)
539 on the low Co loading catalysts (HAP, Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP). For instance,
540 800 ppm are produced over HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts at 500 °C. Indeed, on the
541 Co(1.1)/HAP catalyst CO/ CO_2 ratio is around 6 while it decreases to about 0.01 on the

542 Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst (Table 4). In their study on the CO oxidation reaction on
543 hydroxyapatite Matsumura et al. [35] reported that the introduction of
544 tetrachloromethane into the feedstream in the CO oxidation process converts, at least
545 partially, the hydroxyapatite to chlorinated apatite that suppresses the oxidation of CO
546 to CO₂. We can conclude that the same phenomenon occurs in the case of our prepared
547 HAP and the very low Co loadings catalysts (1.1%), leading to a large uncovered
548 support surface, which inhibited the CO oxidation to form CO₂. By contrast, based on
549 our characterisation results, it seems that deposited Co₃O₄ spinel phase on the catalysts
550 surface, for Co loadings $\geq 4.3\%$, enhances notably the CO conversion to CO₂.

551 The HAP support effect on the distribution of the DCE oxidation products was also
552 studied by analysing the VC intermediate production curves (Fig. 9D). In the case of
553 HAP, Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts a production peak centred at 425 °C is
554 observed before decreasing sharply for $T \geq 425$ °C with high CO production, as above
555 commented. VC concentration maxima result in 800 ppm with HAP, 400 ppm with
556 Co(1.1)/HAP and 310 ppm with Co(IE)-HAP catalyst. Nevertheless, with Co(4.3)/HAP
557 catalyst, the VC production peak was shifts to lower temperatures (375 °C with a
558 maximum about 300 ppm) compared to the low Co loading catalysts ($x \leq 1.1\%$).

559 Likewise, the amount of the produced VC continues to decline with Co loading when it
560 did not exceed 55 ppm on the Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst. This suggests that the catalysts
561 with low Co loadings and more acid sites are more selective to produce VC compound.

562 Our NH₃ adsorption study, described above, pointed out that catalysts with $Co \leq 4.3\%$
563 have higher surface acid density compared to $Co(8.5 \leq x \leq 19.6)$ /HAP catalysts. This is in
564 good agreement with a number of earlier studies in the literature [57-58] which reveal
565 that acid sites may play a key role for the production of VC at mild temperatures as an

566 intermediate molecule derived from hydrodechlorination of DCE, which should readily
567 decompose finally to CO_x.

568 Fig. 9E and Fig. 9F show the production profiles of HCl and Cl₂, respectively.
569 Generally, HCl is the preferred chlorinated product because it can be easily trapped by
570 aqueous scrubbing [58]. As can be seen in Fig. 9E hydrogen chloride is the main deep
571 DCE oxidation product over the HAP, Co(1.1)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts. For
572 instance, over Co(1.1)/HAP catalyst 1800 ppm of HCl are produced at 475 °C compared
573 to 500 ppm produced over Co(8.5)/HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts. However,
574 significant amount of molecular chlorine, Cl₂, is formed on the high Co loadings
575 catalysts, x ≥ 4.5%, due to the occurrence of the Deacon reaction (reaction 8). At 475 °C,
576 the Cl₂ concentration is about 550 ppm on Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst and 420 ppm on the
577 Co(8.5)/HAP catalyst. Furthermore, as shown in Table 4, at 500 °C the Cl₂/HCl values
578 are relatively higher on the Co(4.5 ≤ x ≤ 19.6)/HAP catalysts (0.6-0.9). By contrast, in the
579 case of the HAP, Co(1.1)/HAP and Co(IE)-HAP catalysts very small amounts of Cl₂ are
580 detected in all the reaction temperatures analysed range, up to 500 °C (Cl₂/HCl=0.002-
581 0.005).

583

584 **3.4. Characterisation of used catalysts**

585 Textural, structural and surface chemistry analyses were carried out, on the spent
586 samples, in order to study the eventual changes after reaction. The surface analysis of
587 the used catalysts was conducted by XPS techniques, particularly focused on the
588 determination of chlorine and carbon species deposited on the catalysts surface.
589 According to the reported data in Table 2 the amount of accumulated chlorine on the
590 HAP sample results in around 6.8wt.%. This content tends to increase with Co loading

591 up to 10wt.% on the Co(8.5)/HAP catalyst. However, the XPS analysis shows a lower
592 carbon deposition tendency. Indeed, carbon traces are detected on the low Co loading
593 samples only: Co(1.1)/HAP (1.8%) and Co(IE)-HAP (3%). These results are in
594 accordance with the lower carbon balance values found on these two tested catalysts
595 (72% for Co(IE)-HAP and 78% for Co(1.1)/HAP), as stated in Table 4.

596 Irrespective of the spent catalyst, its characterisation by XRD, Fig. 2B, evidences total
597 conversion of the hydroxyapatite into its chlorinated analogue (Cl-AP: $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{Cl}_2$).
598 The diffractogram of this chlorinated framework is particularly characterised by two
599 intense signals at $2\theta = 31.5^\circ$ and 32.4° (JCPDS: 027-0074). The former seems to
600 overlap the peak, centred at 31.6° , attributed to Co_3O_4 structure. Nevertheless, the
601 presence of the diffraction peak at $2\theta = 37.1^\circ$ proves that the spinel is still present on the
602 spent catalysts. Similar observations concerning the phase transformation of
603 hydroxyapatite were found in the literature [35,36]. For instance, Reichle [36] found
604 that gaseous chlorobenzene could react with hydroxyapatite to yield chlorinated apatite.
605 It should be noted that, although the chlorine amounts retained on the surface exceed
606 those required to form stoichiometric Cl-AP, no additional chlorinated phases, such as
607 cobalt(II) chloride or cobalt(II) chlorate, are detected on the spent catalysts by XRD.
608 Nevertheless, it is known that surface cobalt oxides sites adsorb chlorine which results
609 from the destruction of chlorinated compounds [59]. Fig. 11 depicts the effect of the
610 non exchanged cobalt species on the resulting chlorine amount (surface Cl, %),
611 calculated as the difference between the total chlorine amount and that required to form
612 Cl-AP. The analysis of this figure demonstrates that the chlorine amounts increase with
613 the surface Co species up to 4.1%, corresponding to 8.9% of non exchanged cobalt
614 amount (close to 8.1% for theoretical Co monolayer), after which it stay almost
615 constant. This suggests that chlorine species are adsorbed on the surface Co species.

616 On the other hand, the spinel Co_3O_4 ($2\theta = 37.1^\circ$) diffraction line broadening was used to
617 estimate, by Scherrer equation, the evolution of crystallite size after catalytic test (Table
618 1). In this sense, no significant growth of the spinel crystallites is noticed (size
619 estimated to be around 23-28 nm in the fresh sample while it is around 23-32 nm after
620 catalytic test). The BET surface area of all the analysed catalysts notably decreases after
621 reaction (Table 1). For instance, it decreases from 55 to $44 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in the HAP sample
622 and from 41 to $29 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ in the Co(19.6)/HAP sample. This loss of specific surface area,
623 in all the spent catalysts, is probably due to the phase transformation of HAP support
624 which is converted to Cl-AP [56].

625

626 **3.5. Catalytic stability**

627 The catalytic stability with time on stream of the HAP support and Co(19.6)/HAP
628 catalysts, in the DCE oxidation process, was investigated by analysing the evolution of
629 DCE conversion and the products selectivity with time on stream at 375°C for 50 h
630 (Fig. 12). In spite of a comparable activity of the two catalysts is observed at the
631 beginning of the experiments (80-85%) the HAP suffers a significant decay with time.
632 For instance, after 50 h HAP shows a conversion lower than 55% whereas it is still
633 around 77% over Co(19.6)/HAP catalyst. In fact, this catalyst shows a stable
634 performance in terms of conversion and selectivity after a reaction time interval of 7 h.
635 The observed good stability of this sample is related to the lower impact of induced
636 chlorination. On the basis of the observed decrease in HCl selectivity during the first
637 seven hours, it is reasonable to think that chlorinated apatite is formed at this time
638 interval. Afterwards stable selectivities to HCl (42%) and Cl_2 (58%) are observed.
639 Interestingly chlorination does not involve significant changes in CO_2 selectivity as it
640 remains constant (above 98%) during the whole time span of the run.

641 By contrast, it seems that the HAP catalytic activity is much more affected by its
642 structural transformation to chlorinated apatite. Moreover, the shape of the HAP activity
643 curves versus time on stream reflects an oscillatory behaviour suggesting the
644 intermittent regeneration of the hydroxyapatite by the produced water (equation 9).
645 Reichle [36] also observed the regeneration phenomenon of the hydroxyapatite structure
646 by steam in the hydrolysis of chlorobenzene. As for product distribution high VC and
647 HCl selectivity, 76% and 70% respectively, are achieved together with significant low
648 CO/CO₂ selectivity values (lower than 20%).

649

650 **4. Conclusions**

651 Calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite, with Ca/P ratio of 1.5, was synthesised by
652 precipitation method. The resulted support was impregnated with cobalt and
653 characterised by TEM, BET, XRD, FTIR, H₂-TPR, UV-Visible-NIR DRS, XPS and
654 volumetric adsorption of CO₂ and NH₃ molecules techniques. Three types of cobalt
655 species have been identified in the impregnated Co(x)/HAP catalysts: (i) Co²⁺ ions
656 exchanged with Ca²⁺ ions of the apatite framework, (ii) Co_xO_y clusters with small
657 particle size (<10 nm) and (iii) well crystallised spinel Co₃O₄ structures. The volumetric
658 adsorption study has shown that the addition of high amounts of Co (≥ 8.5%) notably
659 decreases the acid character of the Co(x)/HAP catalysts surface. This is explained by the
660 achievement of Co monolayer densities which cover totally the support surface and,
661 thus, minimise its surface acidity. However, the addition of cobalt (1.1≤x≤19.6) to HAP
662 increases by more than twice its surface basic density.

663 The Co(x)/HAP catalysts have been tested in the oxidation of 1,2-dichloroethane. Due
664 to their improved textural and structural properties the resulting Co/hydroxyapatite
665 catalysts have proved higher activity compared to bulk Co₃O₄. Moreover, the present

666 study points out the effect of the HAP support on the catalytic stability and the
667 distribution of the reaction products. For instance, the low Co loading catalysts have
668 resulted more selective towards intermediate products (CO and VC). However, high
669 stability and high selectivity to produce CO₂, as deep oxidation product, have been
670 favoured by the Co-rich catalysts which contain the easily reducible Co³⁺ and Co²⁺ ions.
671 The characterisation of the spent catalysts has shown that they have retained a
672 significant amount of chlorine which consists of (i) adsorbed chlorine species on the
673 exposed surface of bulk Co₃O₄ and (ii) a fraction that ion-exchanges hydroxide anions
674 leading to the conversion of the hydroxyapatite into its chlorinated analogue.

675

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689 **CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES**

- Table 1 Characterization of the Co(x)/HAP catalysts (Fresh and used in the DCE oxidation)
- Table 2 XPS study of the Co(x)/HAP catalysts (Fresh and used in the DCE oxidation).
- Table 3 Reducibility and surface chemistry of the prepared Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 4 Catalytic data in DCE oxidation over Co(x)/HAP samples.
- Fig. 1 Mesoporous size distribution for the Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP: (A) fresh catalysts and (B) catalysts used in DCE oxidation.
- Fig. 3 (Left) TEM micrographs of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(1.1)/HAP catalysts. (Right) Highlighted visible diffraction plans.
- Fig. 4 FTIR spectra of Co(x)/HAP (A) 4000-400 domain and (B) 1000-500 domain.
- Fig. 5 UV–VIS–NIR spectra of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 6 XPS spectra of Co 2p_{3/2} - Co 2p_{3/2} region for Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 7 H₂-TPR profiles of Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts
- Fig. 8 Amounts of (a) exchanged cobalt and (b) Co forming Co₃O₄ or Co_xO_y phase on the Co(x)/HAP catalysts, as determined by H₂-TPR, versus overall Co content.
- Fig. 9 DCE conversion and products distribution on the Co(IE)-HAP and Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 10 Pseudo-first order fit for the DCE oxidation experimental data over the Co(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Fig. 11 Variation of the surface chlorine amounts for the tested Co(x)/HAP catalysts versus non ion-exchanged Co species amounts.
- Fig. 12 DCE oxidation over HAP and Co(19.6)/HAP catalysts at 375 °C as a function of time on stream.

